

Deliverable 2.2

ROBIN Regions Action Plans

CTA
December 2023

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**DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH**

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ABBREVIATIONS

Table 1. Abbreviations

ACBS	Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy
AND	Andalusia Region
BW	Baden Württemberg Region
CBGMC/CANVAS	Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas
ET	Environmental Tool
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
KP	Knowledge Platform
MARC	Multi-Actor Regional Constellation
N/A	Not Applicable
PDCA	Plan-Do-Check-Act Methodology
PMT	Policy Monitoring Tool
RAM	Regional Analysis Measure
RAP	Regional Action Plan
RCM	Region of Central Macedonia
SA	Support Action
SAP	Support Action Portfolio
SM	Social Measure
SRI	Southern Region of Ireland
SRA	Southern Regional Assembly
TM	Technical Measure
TP	Typology Matrix
ZIL	Zilina Region

Executive Summary

This deliverable is fully focused on explaining all the work developed and the main results obtained from ROBIN task 2.2.

Specifically, this task aims at designing the ROBIN Support Actions and Plans to be implemented by the ROBIN regions, addressing the regional improvement area prioritized and the co-created results of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas (hereinafter CANVAS) obtained during the regional co-creation workshops with MARC members in each region held in the framework of task 2.1 (detailed information available in D2.1).

T2.2 main objectives are:

Development of a portfolio of support actions for regional capacity building in both in technical and social areas, to be used for regional inspiration in building the regional action plans;

Design of Regional Action Plans towards the development and implementation of the regional improvement areas, including (i) the actions to be delivered, (ii) foreseen timing and (iii) resources required for its implementation, among other relevant information;

Organization of a dedicated workshop among all the partners to finetune the regional action plans;

Development of evaluation and monitoring guidelines for the future implementation of the action plans, based in the Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology (hereinafter PDCA), serving also as a tool for the ROBIN toolbox validation plan to be developed in WP3.

The development of the activity under task 2.2. was design in coordination with and considering previous projects results and further work based on the main outcomes obtained:

- Main inputs for T2.2.:
 - Co-creation workshops' results from T2.1. held with the regional MARC members:
 - Identification of the Regional Value Propositions,
 - Information contained in the regional CBGMC.
 - Good practices measures, mainly social ones, obtained from the analysis of deliverable 1.2. (T1.3.)

- Main outputs for other ROBIN work packages:
 - 50 support actions as the main testing fields for the validation of the ROBIN toolbox under WP3
 - PDCA methodology for the design and implementation of the validation methodology

Figure 1. Synergies between T2.2. and other ROBIN work packages and tasks

For the development of the Regional Action Plans several different support materials were developed:

1. The ROBIN Support Action Portfolio: a list of 49 different actions divided into 3 categories (regional analysis, social and technical measures) that served as inspiration for the development of the Regional Action Plans. The Support Actions Portfolio has, as well, a role as part of the ROBIN toolbox.
2. The ROBIN Regional Action Plan template: designed as the base for building the ROBIN Regional Action Plan, including all the relevant information per each support action included.
3. The ROBIN Action Plans Workshop: developed as an internal cross-fertilization workshop among project partners aimed at fostering the development of the different ROBIN Regional Support Action Plans, by answering strategical and operational questions from the partners, with aligned concepts and terms, finetune some relevant aspects, etc. The workshop helped to finetune relevant aspects on the Regional Action Plans. It was physically organized by CTA in MTU Cork's headquarters on the 4th of October 2023, as part of the 3rd project meeting agenda, targeting ROBIN partners.
4. The Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology: as a mechanism for the evaluation of the implementation of the Regional Action Plans designed in WP2 and the development of the validation methodology to be implemented in ROBIN WP3, by helping the regions to enhance the quality management of the action plans, identifying potential needs and changes according to deviations detected due to internal (as potential inefficiencies in the design phase) or external (as variations in the territory needs and circumstances) reasons.

The main results of the work developed within task 2.2. during the 12 months it lasted (M5-M16 of the ROBIN project) have been the development of:

- 5 Regional Action Plans, oriented towards the consecution of the Regional Vision/Value Proposition identified as most important by the project partners and the MARC members of each region during the co-creation workshops implemented in task 2.1. A total of 50 support actions (10 per action plan), fully described, as the testing field for the validation of the ROBIN toolbox under WP3.
- 17 out of the 50 support actions included in the Regional Action Plans are considered social measures.

- All the ROBIN tools are identified as potentially used for the total or partial implementation of at least in one support action during the execution of WP3.

The results of T2.2. are, thus, directly contributing to the following projects KPI:

- KPI-6: Support actions for the development or update of regional / local strategies:
 - Target value: ≈ 50
 - Result obtained: a total of 50 support actions are included in the 5 Regional Action Plans
- KPI-9: New business models and social measures co-created:
 - Target value: > 10
 - Result obtained:
 - 17 social measures included as support actions in the Regional Action Plans.
 - 1 support action aiming at developing a business model
- Coordination support actions:
 - Target value: > 10
 - Result obtained: 49 coordination support actions included in the Support Action Portfolio

1. Introduction

Objective of Work package 2

WP2 has a two-fold approach:

- 1) Co-creating tailored circular bioeconomy governance models and structures with the active involvement of the key actors within each of ROBIN's regions, and
- 2) Design the ROBIN toolbox.

The specific objectives of WP2 are:

- Co-create, new and improved governance models and practices.
- Design and develop the ROBIN tools to guide the integration of regional opportunities.
- Define the appropriate support actions and a plan for providing support in each region.
- Aggregate the project's tools and services for the implementation of sustainable value chains.

Objective of task 2.2 and the regional action plans

This deliverable is fully focused on explaining all the work developed and the main results obtained from ROBIN task 2.2.

Specifically, this task aims at designing the ROBIN Support Actions and Plans to be implemented by the ROBIN regions, addressing the regional improvement area prioritized and the co-created results of Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas (hereinafter CANVAS) obtained during the regional co-creation workshops with MARC members in each region held in the framework of task 2.1 (detailed information available in D2.1).

T2.2 main objectives are:

- Development of a portfolio of support actions for regional capacity building in both technical and social areas, to be used for regional inspiration in building the regional action plans;
- Design of Regional Action Plans towards the development and implementation of the regional improvement areas, including (i) the actions to be delivered, (ii) foreseen timing and (iii) resources required for its implementation, among other relevant information;
- Organization of a dedicated workshop among all the partners to finetune the regional action plans;
- Development of evaluation and monitoring guidelines for the design of the action plans monitoring, based on the Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology (hereinafter PDCA), serving also as a tool for the ROBIN toolbox validation plan to be developed in WP3.

2. Synergies among T2.2. and other ROBIN work packages and tasks

Synergies between task 2.1. and task 2.2.

As previously mentioned, task 2.1. and task 2.2. are directly linked and they can be considered two phases of the co-creation work developed at regional level in collaboration with MARC members and other regional stakeholders, for developing the action plans within WP2:

1. Task 2.1.: Co-creation of the regional governance models and practices with stakeholders. During this task, the basis for the action plans were discussed and agreed with the MARC members in dedicated co-creation workshops. The main results of this phase were:
 - a. The identification of the regional governance improvement area (or value proposition of the CANVAS) based on a prioritization exercise with all the stakeholders.
 - b. An initial list of activities (or support actions) from the CANVAS results, targeted to obtain the regional governance improvement area. This list of activities was used as an inspirational starting point for the development of the regional action plans, and its support actions developed during task 2.2., but the difference in the strategical timeframe between both elements (longer term in the CANVAS and more focused on the ROBIN project duration in the case of the Regional Action Plans) have led to a different, but complementary, approach at regional level.

2. Task 2.2.: Design of the ROBIN Support Actions and Plans. This task is a further step on the development of the ROBIN regional action plans. Based on (i) T2.1. list of activities of each region, (ii) the support actions portfolio gathered by CTA and the (iii) inspiration and insights gained in the dedicated workshop, a more detailed action plan per region was drafted, including support actions supporting the work towards the regional governance improvement area (or value proposition) that could be performed or initiated within the ROBIN project timeline. Distinct strategic timeframes between the CBGMC (longer term) and the ROBIN project duration for Regional Action Plans (RAP) led to separate yet complementary approaches at the regional level.

Synergies between task 2.2. and work package 1

The development of the activity under task 2.2. has been done not only considering the results obtained in task 2.1. but also, relevant information and outputs from work package 1, namely the identification of good practices, with especial emphasis on the social measures, in task 1.3. that have been included as inspirational support actions in the ROBIN Support Action Portfolio (further information on this in ROBIN deliverable D1.2. and in this document in paragraph 2).

Due to the relevance of the social aspects in ROBIN, a dedicated kpi of minimum 2 social support actions per Regional Action Plan were requested, for reaching a total of minimum 10 social support actions in total.

Synergies between task 2.2. and work package 3

Although the development of the validation plans for the ROBIN toolbox under WP3 is still under discussion, the work developed in task 2.2. has been performed considering relevant needed inputs from the latest to the former. This is the case, since the support actions included in T2.2. regional plans are the basis for the validation of the ROBIN tools which will be tested in WP3.

In this sense, as previously explained, some minimum information in each Regional Action Plan has been requested as:

- A minimum number of support actions (kpi > 10)
- A minimum number of social support actions (kpi > 2)
- Analysis of the most suitable tools per support action to be tested.

Additionally, the PDCA methodology guidelines performed in T2.2 (see paragraph 4) can be used and applied in the validation methodology to be developed within WP 3 tasks.

Figure 1. Synergies between T2.2. and other ROBIN work packages and tasks

3. Support materials developed for the performance of the Regional Action Plans

In order to ensure the correct execution of the tasks foreseen in Task 2.2. and to achieve its main objectives (the regional action plans), work has been carried out on the development of support materials which, in many cases, have become ROBIN project tools in themselves, to be included in the ROBIN toolbox.

1) The ROBIN Support Action Portfolio

Within the ROBIN project, the development of the Support Action Portfolio (SAP) has evolved as an iterative and collaborative endeavour, intimately connected with the co-creation efforts encapsulated in task 2.1. and task 2.2. These tasks represent sequential phases in the regional co-creation process involving MARC members and other stakeholders within WP2.

Task 2.1., focusing on the co-creation of regional governance models and practices, laid the foundation for the Support Action Portfolio during dedicated workshops with MARC members. This phase, akin to constructing a value proposition canvas, identified regional governance improvement areas through prioritization exercises.

Task 2.1. outcome, completed with CTA's own knowhow and previous experience. provided an initial list of 40 actions, divided into 3 main categories:

- Regional Analysis Measures (RAM): actions under this category involve in-depth assessments of regional contexts, identifying specific challenges, opportunities, and potential improvements within the governance framework.
- Social Measures (SM): this category encompasses actions targeted at fostering collaboration, engagement, and social cohesion within the regional context. It includes initiatives to enhance awareness, communication, and community involvement.
- Technical Measures (TM): actions classified here are focused on the implementation of practical and technical solutions to address identified governance challenges. This could involve the deployment of technologies, infrastructure improvements, and other technical interventions tailored to the unique needs of each region.

This initial work was complemented through a two-fold approach process:

- a. In depth analysis of D1.2. Good Governance Practices to identify further actions, especially on the social aspects, to be included in the Support Action Portfolio;
- b. Review and contribution from project partners.

The combination of those two actions added 7 new actions on the initial list, all under the Social Measures category.

This ongoing collaboration ensured that the Support Action Portfolio evolved in harmony with the dynamic understanding of regional needs, serving as an inspirational catalyst for both regional action plans and support actions subsequently developed in Task 2.2.

Finally, the finalization of the Regional Action Plans (RAP) prompted a revisit of the Support Action Portfolio, emphasizing a meticulous review to refine its content and enhance its coherence with the defined regional strategies. After this final review step, 2 new actions were included in the Support Action Portfolio.

This intentional revisit post- Regional Action Plans finalization underscores the adaptability and responsiveness of the Support Action Portfolio to the evolving regional contexts, preparing it to be a valuable tool beyond the immediate confines of the ROBIN project, especially for its use as part of the ROBIN toolbox and for replication purposes, as it is conceived as a versatile tool designed not only for immediate application in the context of ROBIN but with a forward-looking intention to be a valuable resource beyond the project's scope.

Table 2. SAP measures added in each SAP building step

Initial list based on T2.1, results and CTA inputs	40 actions
Review based on D1.2. and partners experience	7 actions
Final RAPs review	2 actions
TOTAL	49 actions

Concluding, the ROBIN Support Action Portfolio is including a total of 49 inspirational actions:

- 16 Regional Analysis Measures
- 20 Social Measures
- 13 Technical Measures

The descriptions of the actions within the Support Action Portfolio are intentionally broad and comprehensive, crafted to be used as inspirational raw material and transcend the boundaries of the ROBIN project. This ensures their applicability and utility in diverse regional contexts, fostering sustainability and relevance beyond the immediate project timeframe.

Each measure of the Support Action Portfolio includes the following information, encompassing essential information for strategic implementation and reference purposes:

- Title, describing concisely the specific nature of the support action.
- Type of support action, categorized into one of the three groups: Regional Analysis Measures, Social Measures, or Technical Measures.
- Unique Code for organizational clarity and streamlined communication.
- Description of the support action, outlining its purpose, methodology, and anticipated outcomes.
- ROBIN region/s where the support action is either partially or fully included in the RAP.

It is worth noting that the last section of the profile details the Regional Action Plans (RAP) where these actions have been incorporated. However, it's important to acknowledge that, in many instances, the action described in the Regional Action Plans may not fully cover the comprehensive description provided in the Support Action Portfolio. This distinction emphasizes the nuanced nature of the co-creation process, where the Support Action Portfolio acts as a comprehensive reference

tool, offering detailed insights that go beyond the concise summaries present in the corresponding Regional Action Plans.

A detailed sheet per action with the information mentioned above is available in Annex 1.

2) The ROBIN Regional Action Plan Template

For the development of the Regional Action Plans a tailor-made template was created by CTA trying to include the relevant available information to work with, considering the heterogeneity of the ROBIN regions in terms of

- (i) the value propositions selected and the difference in their strategical vs. operational level,
- (ii) the maturity of the region and availability of information linked to the circular bioeconomy sector and the
- (iii) direct implication of key regional players as partners in the ROBIN consortium.

Each field of information included the following elements:

- 1) Name,
- 2) Level of application:
 - a. Regional Action Plan level (if the field applies for the whole action plan)
 - b. Support Action level (if it applies to each singular support action)
- 3) Description
- 4) Type of answer:
 - a. Numeric
 - b. Open answer
 - c. Predefined answer (drop-down list)

The following fields were included in the Regional Action Plan template:

Table 3. Fields on the Regional Action Plan template

Name	Level	Description	Type
Regional Vision / Value Proposition	Action Plan	Includes the improvement governance area selected from each T2.1 regional co-creation workshops results, and it is clearly indicated in the upper part of the support action plan as its main objective. It's not linked to a specific support action, as it's the main result of the implementation of the ones listed below.	Open answer
How the action plan as a whole drives the regional vision forward (from the co-created governance model)	Action Plan	Includes a clear description on how the action plan drives the regional vision, coming from the results on T2.1.	Open answer
Region name	Action Plan	Name of the region the action plan is focused on	Open answer
Number	Support Action	Used for a quick, clear and unambiguous identification of the action. This field had to follow a correlative sequence among the support actions listed.	Numeric

Title	Support Action	Title of the action	Open answer
Objective of the support action	Support Action	Short information describing the main purpose of the support action	Open answer
Description of the support action	Support Action	Main field within the template to include relevant information about the support action including type of work to develop, detail on the expected results and deliverables, etc.	Open answer
Steps of the support action	Support Action	Preliminary list of steps to design and implement the support action, according to the support action's objectives and description.	Open answer
Regional responsible		Identification of the responsible/s of the implementation of the activity at regional level	Open answer (entities' acronym or name)
Resources needed	Support Action	Pre-identification of potential types of resources needed for the implementation of the support action.	Drop-down list including the following alternatives and examples (more than one could be selected per support action): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial Resources (as securing budgets, grants, or investments to support the action plan's implementation and sustain its progress over time) Human Resources (professionals as project managers, subject matter experts, researchers,

			<p>planners, community organizers, and administrative staff)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Physical Infrastructure (as buildings, transportation systems, communication networks, water supply systems, energy infrastructure, waste management facilities, and others) • Technological Resources (as computers, software applications, data analytics tools, Geographic Information Systems (GIS), sensors, communication devices, and other technological) • Data and Information (gathering and analysing data on demographics, socio-economic indicators, environmental factors, infrastructure status, and other relevant information specific) • Others
Timeframe	Support Action	Approximation of the timeline for the action within each regional action plan. Timeframes cannot be compared between regional action plans as the strategical/operational level of each regional vision may be very different.	<p>Drop-down list including the following alternatives (one per support action):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term • Medium term • Long term
Success Criteria / KPI	Support Action	Identification of target criteria (KPIs) to consider the support action achieved.	Open answer based on SMART approach

Potential Risks	Support Action	Identification of potential risks associated to the support action implementation	<p data-bbox="1252 209 2024 320">Drop-down list including the following alternatives and examples (more than one could be selected per support action):</p> <ul data-bbox="1301 344 2024 1362" style="list-style-type: none"> <li data-bbox="1301 344 2024 496">• Political Risks (as changes in government leadership, policy shifts, or political instability can affect the continuity and support for a regional action plan) <li data-bbox="1301 504 2024 687">• Financial Risks (as insufficient funding or budget constraints can pose a significant risk to the successful execution of a regional action plan, or overestimating available resources or inadequate ones) <li data-bbox="1301 695 2024 879">• Stakeholder Engagement Risks (as inadequate engagement and participation of key stakeholders, including communities, local government bodies, non-governmental organizations, and private sector) <li data-bbox="1301 887 2024 1118">• Implementation Risks (as delays, resource constraints, technical difficulties, or unforeseen obstacles, poor project management, lack of capacity or expertise, or insufficient monitoring and evaluation mechanisms can impact the timely and effective execution of the plan) <li data-bbox="1301 1126 2024 1278">• Environmental and Climate Risks (as increased frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, water scarcity, ecosystem degradation, or threats to biodiversity) <li data-bbox="1301 1286 2024 1362">• Socioeconomic Risks (as poverty, inequality, demographic shifts, or economic downturns. Social
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			<p>tensions, lack of access to resources or services, or economic disparities can hinder implementation efforts and exacerbate existing challenges).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal and Regulatory Risks (as inadequate consideration of legal frameworks, lack of enforcement mechanisms, or conflicting regulations)
Corrective Measures	Support Action	Identification of corrective measures that could prevent the risks for happening or mitigate their impact	Open answer
Linkage With Other Support Actions	Support Action	Identification of linkages with other support actions within the regional action plan (in terms of use of their results or inputs giving).	Open answer (numeric based on the number/s of the support action/s)
Robin Tools	Support Action	Identification of potential ROBIN tools from the ROBIN toolbox to support the action implementation as part of the WP3 validation plan.	<p>Drop-down list including the following alternatives (more than one could be selected per support action):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge Platform • Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas • Policy Tool • Environmental Tool • Support Actions Portfolio • Typology Matrix

3) The ROBIN Action Plans Workshop

As part of the Support Action Plans building support actions, a dedicated 3-hour workshop aiming at fostering the proper development of the different Regional Support Action Plans, answering strategical and operational questions from the partners, align concepts and terms, finetune some relevant aspects, etc, was physically organized by CTA in MTU Cork's headquarters on the 4th of October 2023, as part of the 3rd project meeting agenda, targeting ROBIN partners.

AGENDA – 3rd Project Meeting

Date: 4-5/10/2023 | **Location:** Cork, Ireland

Venue: [Melbourn Building, MTU, Cork](#) | **Remote participation:** [here](#)

Time	Topic	Partner
1 st day		
09.00 - 09.30	Welcome and registration	MTU, QPL
09.30 - 09.40	Overall progress	QPL
09.40 - 10.10	Updates on WP2 (Co-creating governance models and structures) <i>WP overview, activities per Task (objectives, methodology, expected contributions per partner & expected outcomes), action plan by M18</i>	CTA
10.10 - 10.50	Presentation of the ROBIN Tools and Toolbox <i>MTU, AUTH and QPL present the tools that they developed and provide examples. S2I presents the design of the toolbox to receive feedback.</i>	MTU
10.50 - 11.10	Coffee break	
11.10 - 12.10	Governance models and practices co-created <i>Under the coordination of CTA, each regional authority presents the key outcomes and takeaway messages of the T2.1 co-creation workshops</i>	CTA
12.10 - 12.50	Portfolio of support actions for regional capacity building <i>Presentation of the support actions produced in areas such as: raising stakeholder awareness, engaging stakeholders, etc</i>	CTA
12.50 - 14.00	Lunch break	
14.00 - 17.00	Workshop to shape the regional Action Plans <i>A workshop where the regional partners will shape Action Plans detailing the specific support actions that will be offered in their region</i>	CTA
17.00 - 17.00	Wrap-up, conclusions of the 1st day	QPL

Figure 3. Regional Action Plans workshop within the 3rd Project Meeting Agenda

As a preparatory work for the effectiveness of the workshop, all the ROBIN regions were asked to fill in the Action Plan template with the requested information per action plan (see “ROBIN Regional Action Plan Template” for further details).

During the months of July and September 2023, and as part of the workshop preparatory phase, CTA hold bilateral meetings with all the regional nodes to solve doubts and questions about the methodology to fill in the template.

The workshop itself was designed as a collaborative cross-fertilization event among the ROBIN regions with feedback from CTA in key relevant information, having the following agenda structure:

- 1) 5 rounds of 30' presentation per region, split in:
 - a. 20' presentation of the Regional Action Plan draft
 - b. 10' for comments and questions from CTA as strategy expert and the rest of the partners.
- 2) 30' presentation of the Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology guidelines (see paragraph 5 for further information) as a tool for the development of monitoring plans for the Regional Support Action Plans in the future.

As a result of the workshops:

- some regional exchange was performed, having some regions inspired by the presentation and approach followed and explained by other regions,
- some general agreements on approaches and definitions were achieved among the partners at project strategical and operational level,
- some finetuning and recommendations were given by CTA to the regional nodes to improve the action plans in terms of quality, clarity and usefulness of the information included.

With all the information and insights gathered during the action plan workshop, the regions further worked on their regional action plans to finally adjust them and get ready for the work to be developed in WP3.

4) The Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology

The ROBIN project aims to empower Europe's regional authorities to reshape governance structures, accelerating the deployment of circular bioeconomy targets. The objective is to create, through collaboration, governance models that consider the ever-evolving nature of regional contexts and circular bioeconomy aspects.

The PLAN-DO-CHECK-ACT (PDCA) approach has been chosen as the primary methodology to ensure the effectiveness and continuous improvement of these governance models. This document elucidates the PDCA method within the scope of the ROBIN project.

The PLAN-DO-CHECK-ACT (PDCA) cycle is fundamental to continuous improvement and **quality management**. Rooted in the early 20th century, its origins can be traced back to the pioneering work of quality management experts like Walter A. Shewhart. However, Dr. W. Edwards Deming, often considered the father of modern quality control, popularized it.

While Shewhart initially proposed a three-step process, it was Deming who refined it into the four-step PDCA model we know today. Due to this association, the cycle is sometimes also called the Deming Cycle or Shewhart Cycle¹.

The PLAN-DO-CHECK-ACT (PDCA) cycle is a systematic series of steps for the continuous improvement of processes and products. It's a method used to achieve and maintain control of work processes.

Figure 4. Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology scheme

¹ Moen, R., & Norman, C. (2006). Evolution of the PDCA cycle. Nicolet, NA.

Imai, M. (1986). Kaizen: The key to Japan's competitive success. McGraw-Hill/Irwin.

The PDCA cycle is then an **iterative** exercise, meaning it's designed to be repeated over and over as part of a commitment to continuous improvement strategies. In doing so, organizations can identify inefficiencies, test potential solutions, and implement proven changes to improve outcomes over time.

This methodology is widely adopted in various industries and sectors, thanks to its systematic and continuous approach to improvement. In manufacturing, service delivery, and project management alike, the PDCA cycle promotes a culture of continuous learning and improvement.

In essence, PDCA is more than just a methodology. It encapsulates a philosophy of perpetual improvement, emphasizing that there is always room to do better, and the path to excellence is paved with consistent reflection, learning, and adaptation.

Through the years, the PDCA methodology has been an instrumental tool for organizations across industries, guiding them in their quest for operational excellence and higher-quality outputs.

Given the **dynamic nature** of regional governance in the circular bioeconomy domain, it is vital to adopt a flexible, iterative, and responsive method. The PLAN-DO-CHECK-ACT approach provides a structured cycle for continuous improvement, making it apt for ROBIN's aims and objectives.

General overview of the PLAN-DO-CHECK-ACT methodology

As each region has its schemes and starting situation, the guidelines provided need to be clear in the steps definition but flexible enough to allow each region to adapt the methodology to their own needs, considering that the PDCA here explained will be used by the ROBIN project partners, but also other regions during the replication phase and after the project lifetime.

PLAN phase

The planning stage outlines the steps taken to try to change a process or solve a problem. In this step, you will identify and study the issue or change opportunity, create hypotheses on its underlying causes or problems, and select one of these hypotheses to test first.

It involves:

- Design of the core team: Putting together a motivated and skilled team is the first step to a successful deployment of any activity.
- Problem Identification: Pinpointing specific issues or areas of improvement.
- Data Collection: Gathering relevant data to understand the depth and scope of the problem.
- Goal Setting: Determining the desired outcome and setting measurable objectives.
- Strategy Formation: Based on the data collected and the goals set, a strategy or plan of action is formulated to address the problem.

When in the planning phase, considering the following questions could be useful:

- What is the core problem we need to solve or action we need to implement?
- Is this the right problem/action to work on?
- What information do we need to fully understand the problem/action and its root cause?
- Is it feasible to solve/implement it?
- What resources do we need?
- What resources do we have?

- What are some viable solutions?
- What are the measures of success?
- How will the results from a small trial translate to a full-scale implementation?

An affinity diagram might help the team group various ideas throughout this stage. Write down the anticipated outcomes after the course of action has been decided upon. These outcomes will be compared to the final results obtained after the implementation phase (“Do”) during the “Check” stage.

Figure 5. Example of an affinity diagram (source <https://draft.io/>)

DO phase

With a plan in place, the next step is to implement or execute the strategies and actions outlined in the planning phase. The next step is to test the planned solution.

As the PDCA cycle focuses on smaller, incremental changes that help improve processes with minimal disruption, it is recommended to test the planning within a **small-scale project**, preferably in a controlled environment, so you can evaluate the results without interrupting the rest of your operation.

Test your hypothesis You might want to test the solution on one team or within a certain demographic.

It involves:

- Action Implementation: Executing the planned actions on a small or pilot scale to observe the outcomes.
- Stakeholder Engagement: Involving relevant stakeholders to ensure effective implementation.
- Documentation: Recording all processes, results, challenges, and observations during this phase. This will provide essential insights for subsequent phases.

After the initial testing, gather all the relevant data to show if the recognized potential solutions worked or not.

CHECK phase

This step may also be referred to as the “**study**” **phase** (as in the Deming Cycle). It involves a systematic review and analysis of the outcomes post-implementation. It's a crucial step to evaluate the effectiveness of the actions taken.

It involves:

- Data Analysis: Analysing the results against the set objectives from the planning phase.
- Feedback Collection: Gathering feedback from stakeholders and participants.
- Performance Review: Evaluating whether the executed actions led to the desired outcomes. If not, understand why.

The evaluation at this stage will guide relevant decisions in the next step, so it is important to consider the results carefully.

ACT phase

Based on the insights gained from the 'Check' phase, corrective actions can be taken to refine and improve the process. If room for improvement is identified, necessary changes could be included in the “plan” phase, repeating the “do” and “check” phases until a satisfactory result is reached. The evaluation at this stage will guide further strategic decisions in the methodology, so it is important to consider the results carefully. This phase is crucial for the **continuous improvement impact**.

It involves:

- Process Refinement: Tweaking or modifying strategies based on the results and feedback.
- Scaling: If the pilot or small-scale implementation was successful, consider scaling the actions to a broader context.
- Iterative Review: Using the insights from the 'Act' phase to loop back to the 'Plan' phase if necessary, ensuring continuous improvement.

Figure 6. Overview of the PDCA methodology

Implementation within the ROBIN Project Context

The PDCA methodology is foreseen within the ROBIN Project as a **tool for the evaluation of the implementation** of the Regional Action Plans designed in WP2. As previously explained, a correct and well-defined PDCA methodology would help the regions to enhance the quality management of the action plans, identifying potential needs and changes according to deviations detected due to internal (as potential inefficiencies in the design phase) or external (as variations in the territory needs and circumstances) reasons.

For this reason, the PDCA methodology can also be of inspiration for the validation methodology to be implemented in ROBIN WP3, using totally or partially the steps defined below.

To design a successful and useful PDCA methodology for the design and deployment of the ROBIN regional governance models, the following steps may be followed, aligned to the methodology developed with the project, and going beyond it:

a) PLAN phase:

1. Putting together a motivated and skilled team is the first step to a successful deployment of any activity. The team may be made up of employees of the regional or local government with assistance from outside specialists (advisors).

2. The team must gather the relevant background information after being set up, by assessing the current bioeconomy landscape in the targeted European regions. This involves understanding existing governance structures, stakeholder involvement, barriers, and regional specificities.
3. By mapping out the present state, the ROBIN project can formulate objectives tailored to the unique needs and challenges of each region, ensuring that their circular bioeconomy targets are aligned with regional realities. This action is performed using some of the ROBIN tools developed within the project as the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Model Canvas, the Action Plan template and the Support Actions.
4. As main result of this phase, the region would have:
 - a. A regional priority identified to work in, with the development of a specific new governance model.
 - b. A strategic CANVAS to develop the governance model structure.
 - c. An action plan including the following information:
 - i. Activity
 - ii. Description of the activity
 - iii. Responsible team
 - iv. Resources needed
 - v. Time frame
 - vi. Success criteria/KPI
 - vii. Potential risks
 - viii. Corrective measures
 - ix. Linkage with other activities

The plan phase can be directly identified with the work developed by the ROBIN regions under T2.1. and T2.2.

b) DO phase:

1. Engaging with key regional stakeholders and other resources needed for the action according to the action plan.
2. Develop the actions identified within the action plan as the first piloting of the innovative governance models. The ROBIN tools included in the toolbox can support this action.
3. Documenting the implementation process, capturing insights on what works, challenges faced, and the responses to those challenges. It's important to measure the results and KPIs obtained, following the same unit of measurement chosen within the PLAN phase for each activity.

The DO phase can be partially identified with the work developed by the ROBIN regions under T4.1. Depending on the timeline of the actions, the DO phase can be finalised after the end of the ROBIN project.

c) CHECK phase:

1. Identify a CHECK committee with responsible and periodic deadlines to act.
2. Collect the relevant KPIs from the previous phase.

3. Compare them to the success criteria included in the planning stage (KPIs on the action plan).
4. Assess if the result is already satisfactory and the actions are already working according to the objective, or if they need further improvements to achieve the overall goal.

Depending on the timeline of the actions, the CHECK phase can be performed and, thus, finalised after the end of the ROBIN project.

d) ACT phase:

1. Identify an ACT committee with responsible and periodic deadlines to decide on potential reactions according to the results obtained in the CHECK phase as described below. The ACT committee could be the same as the CHECK one, or some different roles and capabilities may differ (ie. The ACT committee could need some strategic and decision-making roles, while the CHECK can be more focused on the operational implementation and results from the development of activities).
2. If, as a result of the CHECK phase, all went according to the initial plan, this new process now becomes the baseline for future PDCA iterations, scaling successful pilots and extending the benefits of effective governance models across broader contexts within the region.
3. If further adjustments are needed, it's needed to go back to the first stage – PLAN – and design other alternatives that could work to solve the problem. This could involve introducing new tools from the ROBIN toolbox or tweaking existing ones. Continuously revisiting the 'Plan' phase, ensuring the iterative nature of the PDCA cycle and adapting to evolving regional needs and challenges.

Depending on the timeline of the actions, the ACT phase can be performed and, thus, finalised after the end of the ROBIN project.

In essence, the integration of the PDCA methodology into the ROBIN project offers a structured and iterative approach, ensuring that the strategies and actions remain relevant and effective in promoting a circular bioeconomy across diverse European regions.

Benefits of the PDCA Cycle

The PDCA methodology, with its iterative and systematic approach, provides a range of benefits to stakeholders involved in a regional action plan. Here's a comprehensive look at how stakeholders stand to gain:

PDCA Benefits:

- **Structured Decision-making:** PDCA offers a well-defined framework that guides the design, implementation, assessment, and refinement of policies and governance models.
- **Emphasis on Sustainability:** The iterative nature of PDCA ensures that sustainability remains an ongoing commitment, consistently evaluated and reinforced through successive cycles.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Adhering to the structured phases of PDCA allows stakeholders to demonstrate diligence and transparency in their processes, enhancing trust among the public and stakeholders.
- **Clear Roadmap:** The PDCA cycle provides a step-by-step guide to implementation, ensuring a methodical and purpose-driven approach.
- **Feedback-Driven Approach:** By collecting real-time feedback during the CHECK phase, stakeholders can ensure that governance models remain aligned with practical realities.
- **Collaborative Ecosystem:** Engaging with a wide spectrum of regional actors throughout the PDCA cycle fosters an environment of shared responsibility, mutual learning, and collective growth.

In essence, the PDCA cycle serves for the foundation of a Regional Action Plan, offering stakeholders a structured, transparent, and adaptable methodology for the monitoring of the plan. It ensures that governance models, while firmly rooted in robust principles, remain agile, responsive, and continuously evolving.

4. ROBIN Regional Action Plans

As the main result of the work develop in T2.2. the regions completed their Regional Action Plans, according to the first insights gained from the MARC members in the co-creation workshops (ROBIN task T2.1., information available in D2.1.).

This Regional Action Plans will serve as the test field for the ROBIN toolbox validation under WP3.

As previously mentioned, some ex-ante requirements were set and agreed among the ROBIN regions for the development of the Regional Action Plans, that should include:

- 1) A minimum of 10 support actions with a partial or total implementation foreseen within the ROBIN project timeline, to achieve a global kpi of at least 50 support actions.
- 2) A minimum of 2 support actions under the category of “social measures”, to achieve a global kpi of at least 10 social support actions.
- 3) Not all the support actions should identify a ROBIN tool from the toolbox.
- 4) Not all the Regional Action Plans had to include all the ROBIN tools at least once.
- 5) All the ROBIN tools had to be selected in one support action at least, considering the 5 Regional Action Plans’ support actions.

Andalucia (Spain)

REGIONAL VISION/VALUE PROPOSITION:

Strengthening of regional tools and plans for the promotion and dissemination of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia. Challenges to the potential creation of a circular bioeconomy node in the agrifood value chain

HOW THE ACTION PLAN AS A WHOLE DRIVES THE REGIONAL VISION FORWARD (FROM THE CO-CREATED GOVERNANCE MODEL):

In Andalusia the support actions will help us to collect information about the regional bioeconomy ecosystem of stakeholders and infrastructures, and further build the capacities of the stakeholders and citizens to network and collaborate. All these actions will support the achievement of our long-term regional vision, which is the development of a circular bioeconomy node with the participation of all actors and with a territorial approach.

Nº) Support action	1) Identification of key stakeholders for regional bioeconomy development
Objective of the support action	To identify and analyse the key relevant stakeholders who play a significant role in the regional bioeconomy. It implies including stakeholders of the Andalusian quadruple helix.
Description of the support action	This action is the first step to develop the circular bioeconomy in the region. The identification of key stakeholders for regional bioeconomy development will allow the construction of value chains and the generation of a market for bio-based products in Andalusia.
Steps of the support action	1) CAP/IFA/CTA will analyse the selection of the most suitable stakeholders for circular bioeconomy development based on their experience and participation in various initiatives. 2) CAP/IFA/CTA will create a stakeholders database that will include their interests, objectives, and priorities. For this purpose, a survey will be designed encompassing these items and reports from the region will be analysed.
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA/CTA
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 database of relevant stakeholders
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Regular review and update of the database of stakeholders to ensure it remains comprehensive and up to date.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio

Nº) Support action	2) Awareness raising about circular bioeconomy potential as study field and job career among young and students
Objective of the support action	To provide young and students with information about the potential of circular bioeconomy as studying subject and potential job career, aligned to academia offer in the region and private sector needs, in dedicated events.
Description of the support action	This action seeks to involve young people, especially students aged 18 to 35. CAP has submitted a proposal to participate in the "Bioeconomy Changemakers Festival" which is an event launched and organized by the European Commission in Brussels to unlock the potential of the bioeconomy. IFA will also organize a demonstration and dissemination activity aimed at young students of agricultural and agroforestry training, to be held in the coming months.
Steps of the support action	1) CAP together with other organizations in the region and with Research Centres and Universities will be in charge of carrying out a dissemination day on 14 or 15 March 2024 in Seville and parallel cities: Cordoba, Almeria, Granada, etc. 2) In parallel, dissemination messages about what the circular bioeconomy is and means will be spread during the week of 11-15 March 2024 in the main streets of the city of Seville and on university campuses. 3) IFA will organize a demonstration and dissemination seminar where agricultural sustainability practices developed in the field of bioeconomy will be presented on 18 December 2023.
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA
Resources needed	Human Resources/Financial Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	2 events to involve students linked to the circular bioeconomy field
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Reach out to the most relevant Research Centres and Universities of Andalusia
Linkages with other support actions	1
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio

Nº) Support action	3) Networking activities among all relevant regional, national and international stakeholders
Objective of the support action	To inspire and provide participants with an opportunity to network with regional, and national stakeholders. It aims to engage all stakeholders.
Description of the support action	This action aims to involve all the key agents for the development of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia. In addition, CAP and IFA will collaborate in the participation of key agents from other Central American regions to establish synergies and international cooperation channels for the development of the Andalusian circular bioeconomy.
Steps of the support action	1) CAP will organize on November 21, 2023, a Circular Bioeconomy Forum, which will be a meeting point for administrations, institutional leaders, public-private entities, entities representing civil society and those responsible for bioeconomy projects of interest, both at a regional and national level as well as European and Central American. 2) CAP and IFA are collaborating in the framework of the INTERCOONECTA project to share the Andalusian experience and to establish synergies for the development of the circular bioeconomy.
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA
Resources needed	Human Resources/Financial Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	20 stakeholders from the quadruple helix
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Clear communication and a specific engagement plan/Reach out to all regional and national stakeholders.
Linkages with other support actions	1
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio

Nº) Support action	4) Regional situation diagnosis
Objective of the support action	The objective of this action is based on: 1) Identification of key sectors and industries with growth potential in the bioeconomy. 2) Updating of biomass resources in the region 3) Analysis of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the region's bioeconomy. 4) Identification of challenges and barriers to be addressed for bioeconomic development.
Description of the support action	The updating of the regional situation diagnosis is a crucial activity for the development of bioeconomy. It involves gathering and analysing data on the current state of the region's natural resources, economic activities, and social dynamics. This information is essential for identifying the potential areas of growth and development in the bioeconomy sector. The input for this activity includes collecting data from various sources such as government reports, scientific studies, and stakeholder consultations. This data is then analysed to understand the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the region's bioeconomy.
Steps of the support action	CAP, IFA and CTA will compile all this information into a report, through: 1) Analysing relevant documents from the region. 2) Contacting key stakeholders. 3) Conducting stakeholder surveys.
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA/CTA
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Regional situation diagnosis by means of a report (1)
Potential risks	Not enough data available/information
Corrective measures	Defined methodology to update the information/Contact key stakeholders
Linkages with other support actions	1
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

Nº) Support action	5) Alignment of the regional bioeconomy strategy with regional strategies and legislation
Objective of the support action	The aim of this activity is to analyse regional strategies and legislation in which the circular bioeconomy can play a relevant role.
Description of the support action	This activity requires conducting a comprehensive analysis of the existing regional strategies to identify areas of synergy and potential collaboration. This involves studying the goals, objectives, and priorities of the regional strategies and assessing how they can be integrated into the bioeconomy strategy.
Steps of the support action	CAP will review and analyse alignments of bioeconomy strategy with: 1) Andalusian Economy Circular Law. 2) Common Agricultural Policy. 3) Environment Strategy. 4) Andalusian Agri-food Sector Competitiveness Plan 5) Agri-environmental measures applied to the agricultural sector. 6)Etc.
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Report on the review of the alignment of the bioeconomy strategy with other regional strategies and legislation.
Potential risks	Not enough data available/information
Corrective measures	Defined methodology to update the information/Contact regional authorities.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	6) Updating of Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy
Objective of the support action	The objective is to update the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) according to the normative and actual situation of the region.
Description of the support action	The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy was approved in 2018 with a framework until 2030, so a review is necessary to adapt it to the current situation at regional level.
Steps of the support action	CAP will be responsible for reviewing the document according to the following steps: 1) Update current actions and measures (18 measures and 41 actions). 2) Preparation of monitoring indicators for the implementation of the ACBS, in collaboration with JRC (Joint Research Centre of the EC). 4) Increase the focus on awareness and communication activities about the circular bioeconomy. 5) Administrative simplification and the use of new technologies. 6) Adapt to new regional and European regulatory and planning developments.
Regional responsible	CAP
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Updated Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy
Potential risks	Not enough data available
Corrective measures	Defined methodology to update the information
Linkages with other support actions	5
ROBIN tool/s	Policy tool

Nº) Support action	7) Identification of bioeconomy research infrastructures at the regional level
Objective of the support action	The objective is to identify existing research infrastructures at the regional level for the development of the bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	The identification of these infrastructure is important to answer the actual and future needs of the industry and surrounding ecosystem at local, regional and national levels, in order the development of the bioeconomy.
Steps of the support action	1) IFA will identify its centres that develop circular bioeconomy activities: agriculture and fisheries. 2) CTA will analyse the research centres at an Andalusian level in the agri-food value chain, including analysis of potential synergies with the bio-based centres design and implementation (according to CTA participation in the BIObec project) 3) Development of a common database with all the research infrastructures identified.
Regional responsible	IFA/CTA
Resources needed	Data and Information Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Database with research infrastructures identified.
Potential risks	Not enough data available or problems to access to it.
Corrective measures	Defined methodology to identify bioeconomy research infrastructures. Contact and engagement of key stakeholders as source of relevant information
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

N°) Support action	8) Identification of possible sources of funds and an analysis of financing opportunities for the development of the regional bioeconomy
Objective of the support action	The objective of this action is the identification of possible sources of funds and an analysis of financing opportunities for the development of the regional bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	This activity includes identifying possible sources of funds and conducting an analysis of financing opportunities. This analysis helps in determining the financial resources available to potentially support the implementation process of activities linked to circular bioeconomy at regional level.
Steps of the support action	1) CTA will review potential programmes of public funding at regional, national and European level for circular bioeconomy initiatives and projects. 2) CTA will analyse the possible sources of private funding and potential investors in the development of the circular bioeconomy in the region. 3) CTA will create a diversified funding portfolio.
Regional responsible	CTA
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Report with sources of funds and investors for circular bioeconomy initiatives and projects.
Potential risks	Not enough data available.
Corrective measures	Defined methodology to identify sources of funds.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	CBMGC Policy tool

Nº) Support action	9) Development of communication plan to increase awareness about circular bioeconomy
Objective of the support action	The objective of this action is the development of a communication plan aimed mainly at civil society.
Description of the support action	The activity involves the development of a comprehensive communication plan, mainly addressing civil society, which includes defining what is the bioeconomy and the advantages and disadvantages for the bioeconomy development.
Steps of the support action	1) CAP, IFA and CTA will elaborate a communication plan and design a campaign to civil society for explaining what the bioeconomy is, and the advantages and disadvantages for the bioeconomy development. 2) CAP, IFA and CTA will implement the actions planned in the communication plan.
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA/CTA
Resources needed	Human Resources Financial Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 Communication Plan
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks Financial Risks
Corrective measures	Regional stakeholder engagement strategy Identification of synergies and potential collaboration with other workshops and events from CAP/IFA/CTA or other key stakeholders for the communication plan implementation.
Linkages with other support actions	6
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio"

Nº) Support action	10) Analysis of the potential constitution of a bioeconomy circular node at regional level
Objective of the support action	The objective is to analyse the steps and gather relevant information for the constitution of a bioeconomy circular node in Andalusia.
Description of the support action	Definition of a dedicated node for bioeconomy in Andalusia, with a clear organisational structure that outlines roles, responsibilities, and reporting procedures within the node. This node will serve as a central hub for coordinating and implementing the region's bioeconomy strategy, fostering collaboration between stakeholders, and providing support and guidance to businesses and research institutions.
Steps of the support action	CAP/IFA/CTA will develop the following actions: 1) Analysis of key stakeholders. 2) Analysis of potential organizational structure at technical, administrative, financial and legal level. 3) Workshop and contacts with other experiences that have implemented this type of structure (Catalonia and another European region)."
Regional responsible	CAP/IFA/CTA
Resources needed	Human Resources Financial Resources
Time frame	Long term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 report with a defined structure of circular bioeconomy node to develop in the following years.
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Defined methodology to develop the Andalusian circular bioeconomy node.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

Baden Wuerttemberg (Germany)

REGIONAL VISION/VALUE PROPOSITION:

To identify, involve and support relevant stakeholders for the development and expansion of the bioeconomy in Baden-Wuerttemberg (BW) and to foster the collaboration with other regions at national and European level.

HOW THE ACTION PLAN AS A WHOLE DRIVES THE REGIONAL VISION FORWARD (FROM THE CO-CREATED GOVERNANCE MODEL):

In Baden-Wuerttemberg the support actions will bring the regional bioeconomy forward and will help us to initiate new impulse in the local cooperation and in opening up new subject areas in the bioeconomy.

Nº) Support action	1) Identification of previous topics in the implementation of the bioeconomy in BW
Objective of the support action	To find topics in the bioeconomy sector in BW who had been implemented them until now in BW.
Description of the support action	To get an overview which topics where until now implemented in the bioeconomy sector in BW.
Steps of the support action	Research which topics were implemented in the last bioeconomy strategy.
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	One research will be done (report)
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	To use the bioeconomy strategy of BW and ministries to get information about status quo of implemented topics in BW.
Linkages with other support actions	3, 4, 5, 7
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

Nº) Support action	2) Identification of gaps in the implementation of the bioeconomy in BW
Objective of the support action	To find topics in the bioeconomy sector in BW who are relevant to implement them in BW and which are forward-looking for BW.
Description of the support action	Organise one workshop to identify topics and requests from stakeholders in BW. Deepen into which topics are missing in the bioeconomy in BW.
Steps of the support action	Workshop with relevant stakeholders in BW in the topic bioeconomy to identify missing topics.
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	one workshop will be done, stakeholder involved.
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Encouraging participative and dialog-oriented formats / Gain support of local administration and actors through the bioeconomy-related "Beispielregionen" in BW
Linkages with other support actions	3,4,5,7
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

N^o) Support action	3) Creation of more matchmaking opportunities between stakeholders around the same topic
Objective of the support action	To promote networking activities to bring experts in the same topic together for discussing.
Description of the support action	Continue existing networks as Fachinitiativen/Netzwerkinitiativen e.g. to the topic Phytopharmaceuticals, Vertical Farming or Start-ups in the bioeconomy to bring experts of one topic together and facilitate exchange.
Steps of the support action	1) Make network meetings in 2024 for experts 2) Identify one more topic for a new network
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Involve 1 or 2 new experts in networks, find one more topic for a new network.
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Good knowledge of the skill competences of the members of such networks
Linkages with other support actions	3
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio

N°) Support action	4) Define target groups in the bioeconomy sector
Objective of the support action	To define target groups which are relevant in the bioeconomy sector for BW.
Description of the support action	Identification of target groups along the whole value chain. Previous/current work of BIOPRO by mobilising different sectors of the regional bioeconomy could be used.
Steps of the support action	1) Identify which target groups are still available in BW 2) Find one or two more target groups
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Identify one or two target groups
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Working with regional cluster managers & chambers of commerce to engage some hesitating companies and organisations from different sectors.
Linkages with other support actions	4, 5, 6, 7
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	5) Identification of gaps in the education sector related to the bioeconomy
Objective of the support action	To see what is missing in the higher education sector (universities) in the bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	Encourage cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary collaboration in the bioeconomy sector. Make interviews with educational institutions like bioeconomy-related universities to know the needs for a targeted education in the topic bioeconomy.
Steps of the support action	1) Short research how the higher education sector has been set until now 2) Make one or three interviews with education institution to find out what is missing
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Literature Research, one to three interviews
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Educational approach based on systemic thinking.
Linkages with other support actions	3
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio

N°) Support action	6) Identification of gaps in the communication material for civil society
Objective of the support action	To get an overview of communication material for civil society to see what can be supplemented to improve the material.
Description of the support action	Two-four Interviews with representatives of the civil society to find out what information is missing and how bioeconomy can trigger social innovation.
Steps of the support action	1) Short research what communication material for civil society there are in BW 2) Make two or four interviews with civil society what is missing or what can be improved to make the material better
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Short report, two or four interviews
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Targeted communication channels depending on the societal group addressed e.g. social media for youth
Linkages with other support actions	3, 4
ROBIN tool/s	Support Actions Portfolio

N°) Support action	7) Inform civil society about the topic bioeconomy
Objective of the support action	To involve civil society to help create a more informed and aware society in the BW region regarding bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	Expand information about the bioeconomy, strengthen social dialogue and promote sustainable development in the region via print media, digital platforms, and educational institutions.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) To identify current communication channels available in BW 2) To search civil society activities examples of other regions 3) To discuss with regional authorities about possible gaps and improvement opportunities 4) To prepare a report with suggestions
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Short report with suggestions
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Good knowledge of gaps in communication (see Action 5)
Linkages with other support actions	5
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge platform

N°) Support action	8) Identification of gaps in funding schemes related to the bioeconomy
Objective of the support action	To evaluate and improve current bioeconomy funding schemes to better match the needs of stakeholders.
Description of the support action	Organise 1 Workshop with funding agencies related to the bioeconomy calls and write a report on gaps and improvement mechanisms.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Meeting with regional authorities 2) Identification of gaps by companies (results first ROBIN workshops + further survey) 3) Review of available reports-Workshop with funding agencies 4) Report with suggestions for improvement
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 regional report on gaps and improvement mechanisms
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Know companies' needs (e.g. scale-up) and address them wherever necessary
Linkages with other support actions	2, 3, 4, 5
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

N°) Support action	9) Thematic exchange with other federal states of Germany
Objective of the support action	To exchange information and experiences with other regions for mutual learning and promotion of the bioeconomy in Germany.
Description of the support action	Workshop with representatives of authorities, innovation agencies, clusters or projects from other German federal states related with the regional implementation of bioeconomy structures.
Steps of the support action	1) Identification of the states with a bioeconomy strategy or plan 2) Identification of contact person 3) organisation of workshop (online or during a planned event) 4) Collaboration plan
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Number of federal states contacted
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Accurate selection of the regions and their spokespersons
Linkages with other support actions	1
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

N°) Support action	10) Mutual exchange on governance structures for the bioeconomy with other regions in EU
Objective of the support action	To exchange information and experiences with other regions for mutual learning and promotion of the bioeconomy in Europe
Description of the support action	Organise 1 mutual learning workshop with another ROBIN region; activity collated to ROBIN task 4.2.
Steps of the support action	1) Organisation of a workshop (T4.2) 2) Preparation of a memorandum of collaboration
Regional responsible	BPRO/S2I
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Number of EU regions involved
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Accurate selection of the governmental bodies/departments to be visited
Linkages with other support actions	1
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

Central Macedonia (Greece)

REGIONAL VISION/VALUE PROPOSITION:

Development of Bioeconomy Cluster in Region of Central Macedonia (RCM) with all actors

HOW THE ACTION PLAN AS A WHOLE DRIVES THE REGIONAL VISION FORWARD (FROM THE CO-CREATED GOVERNANCE MODEL):

In RCM the support actions will help to collect information about the regional bioeconomy ecosystem of stakeholders and infrastructures, and further build the capacities of the stakeholders to network, collaborate, and achieve business success. All these actions will support the achievement of the region's long-term regional vision, which is the development of Bioeconomy Cluster in Central Macedonia with the participation of all actors.

Nº) Support action	1) Networking activities among relevant regional stakeholders
Objective of the support action	The key objective of this action is to inspire and provide participants with an opportunity to network with local bioeconomy ecosystem players.
Description of the support action	The “Bioeconomy Changemakers festival” is an event launched and organized by the European Commission in Brussels to unlock the potential of the bioeconomy. A limited number of 'satellite' events will be organised all over the EU. In this context, 3 EU-funded projects ROBIN, GenB and BioGov.net are joining forces to organise a Bioeconomy Career Info Day event as a satellite event in Thessaloniki, on the 14th of March. The event aims to benefit local youth first by raising awareness about the different career paths towards a successful career in the bioeconomy (including job profiles and skills). Second, the event aims to inspire through successful initiatives and individuals operating in the regional/national bioeconomy market using storytelling. Finally, the event will provide participants with an opportunity to network with local bioeconomy ecosystem players, get informed about the local policy landscape and express their needs/ recommendations directly to local policymakers. Stakeholders from the quadruple helix, including policymakers, industry, research and education institutes, NGOs, entrepreneurs, etc. will be invited to the event, exploiting connections with existing networks.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) QPL reaches out to the other two EU-funded projects (GenB and BioGov.net) to commonly agree on the organisation of the event and the allocation of roles. 2) QPL, in collaboration with the other projects, prepares and submits the application to the European Commission and monitors the progress. 3) Should the application be accepted, QPL configures all the details of the event (the place, invited stakeholders, the agenda, etc), sends invitations to stakeholders (mainly by email) and generates all the necessary materials, including presentations and communication materials. 4) On the day of the event, QPL moderates all the sessions, helps participants to know each other, and, in the end, gets feedback from the participants. 5) Finally, it reports the activities and outcomes of this action into a text that will be incorporated into the T3.2 deliverable.
Regional responsible	QPL
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	It aims to engage as many regional stakeholders as possible (at least 15) and many students too (at least 30).
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	A social media campaign will support promotional efforts.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	2) Food waste in terms of analysis of biomass resources and potential
Objective of the support action	Analysis of food waste produced from food processing units (recording resources and potential).
Description of the support action	The development of a cluster requires the definition of its activities and value proposition. One idea is that it provides its members with networking and collaboration opportunities, useful material and access to critical information, as well as well-targeted support for the transition to bioeconomy. In this context, the current action will analyse the biomass resources in the region, focusing mainly on food waste and will assess their potential for various applications. RCM will communicate with the food industry stakeholders in order to gather all the waste and use it for energy production. The outcome of the action would be a short report with a mapping of the available mass and all the outcomes of the above analysis. This information can be used by policymakers, investors, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding the development of biomass-based industries and the implementation of sustainable energy strategies.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Preparation of Questionnaires to be filled 2) Communication with biogas plants to provide all relevant information regarding their inlets 3) Communication with all Region's Dpts of Industry to provide all relevant information about food processing units and their waste. 4) Data Processing 5) Report
Regional responsible	RCM
Resources needed	Data and Information Human Resources
Time frame	Long term
Success Criteria/ KPI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Region's department of Industry responsiveness / possible lack of available time • Region's gas plants responsiveness • Human Resources sufficiency (including our own department) • Quality and quantity of gathered information
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Clear communication and a specific engagement plan
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	3) Development of regional economy observatory
Objective of the support action	Development of regional economy observatory by the department of Industry, Energy and Natural Resources, Directorate of Environment, Industry, Energy and Natural Resources.
Description of the support action	Another action that supports the development of a cluster is the establishment of a comprehensive database for monitoring, analysing, and disseminating information related to the bioeconomy sector. More specifically, data will be collected and analysed from a wide range of sources, including government agencies, research institutions, and industry stakeholders on various aspects of the bioeconomy, including the production and consumption of bio-based products, the utilization of renewable resources, and the impact of bioeconomy activities on the environment and society. Furthermore, qualitative information, such as best practices, case studies, and success stories will facilitate the identification of emerging trends and opportunities in the sector, allowing stakeholders to capitalize on them and drive innovation. A regional observatory may facilitate negotiation and collaboration between observatories, forging links across government departments and other potential regional, national or international stakeholders.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Research of generic circular bioeconomy data 2) Estimation of the base line situation of the RCM using the environmental protection planning tool 3) Communication with biogas plants / recycling plants to provide all available information- 4) Communication with all Region's departments of Industry and Environment to provide all available information 5) Analysis of good practices 6) Data Processing 7) Base line Report 8) Communication with stakeholders 9) Providing all relevant information to employees/consultants 10) Annual Reports 11) Training seminars, workshops under the auspices of RCM
Regional responsible	RCM
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Long term
Success Criteria/ KPI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Region's department of Industry responsiveness / possible lack of available time • Region's gas plants responsiveness • Human Resources sufficiency (including our own department) • Quality and quantity of gathered information
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Clear communication and a specific engagement plan
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Environmental protection planning tool

Nº) Support action	4) Identification of bioeconomy good practices at regional level
Objective of the support action	The action seeks to identify and analyse effective bioeconomy practices. This will equip industry actors in Central Macedonia with actionable insights for their transition from linear to circular operations in the bioeconomy. Furthermore, the action aims to offer valuable resources, networking, and collaboration opportunities, ensuring a seamless transition to bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	The development of a cluster requires the definition of its activities and value proposition. One idea is that it provides its members with networking and collaboration opportunities, useful material and access to critical information, as well as well-targeted support for the transition to bioeconomy. In this context, the current action will identify and analyse good practices that industry actors in the region of Central Macedonia could use to facilitate their participation in the bioeconomy transition, drifting from linear to circular thinking and operation. In practice, AUTH will build on the practices gathered previously by ROBIN and select those that are more pertinent to the regional context or identify new best practices. The culmination of this effort will be a concise report detailing these practices, which will serve as a guide for industry actors in Central Macedonia, offering them practices emulating or draw inspiration from.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Review Previous Findings: Start by revisiting practices previously identified by ROBIN. 2) Identify Relevant Practices: analyse and select practices that align closely with the regional context of Central Macedonia and identify, if possible, any new best practices that can further aid the transition. 3) Compile the Findings and Drafting of the Report: Organize the identified practices and create a concise report detailing the identified best practices. 4) Dissemination: Distribute the report to industry actors in Central Macedonia, providing them with actionable insights and practices to emulate or draw inspiration from.
Regional responsible	AUTH
Resources needed	Data and Information, WP1 deliverables
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	3-5 practices identified 1 report completed
Potential risks	Not enough data available/information per good practice identified
Corrective measures	Defined research methodology/contact key stakeholders of the good practices for more information
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

N°) Support action	5) Identification of bioeconomy research infrastructures at regional level
Objective of the support action	To accelerate the transition to bioeconomy in Central Macedonia, this action aims to pinpoint key research infrastructures. By identifying facilities and resources currently in use or potential assets for industry actors, academia, and other stakeholders, the action seeks to provide a comprehensive overview of the research infrastructure landscape.
Description of the support action	In line with the above, AUTh will identify research infrastructures in the region of Central Macedonia that industry actors, academia and other stakeholders are using or could use for research and innovation purposes to accelerate the transition to bioeconomy. This process will involve mapping out existing research infrastructures currently in use and evaluating the potential of these infrastructures for research and innovation in the bioeconomy sector. The ultimate goal is to compile these findings into a concise report, offering stakeholders a clear understanding of available and potential research infrastructures in the region.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Research and Data Collection: Conduct a thorough investigation to identify existing research infrastructures in Central Macedonia. 2) Engage with Stakeholders: Consult industry actors, academia, and other stakeholders to gather insights on currently used infrastructures and potential assets. 3) Analysis: Evaluate the potential of identified infrastructures for research and innovation in the bioeconomy sector. 4) Compilation and Drafting of the Report: Organize the collected data and insights into a structured format and create a report of the identified research infrastructures. 5) Dissemination: Distribute the report to relevant stakeholders, providing them with a comprehensive overview of research infrastructures in the region.
Regional responsible	AUTh
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	<p>2 infrastructures identified</p> <p>2-3 stakeholders engaged for data collection</p> <p>1 report delivered</p>
Potential risks	Not enough data available
Corrective measures	Defined research methodology/contact key stakeholders for more information
Linkages with other support actions	N/A (but linked with activities held in WP1)
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	6) Business support and social entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy remit
Objective of the support action	The key objective of this action is to provide business development support services to regional actors (potential cluster members).
Description of the support action	QPL will develop innovation and business development support services to support SMEs, start-ups, or other organisations to participate in the bioeconomy transition, drifting from linear to circular thinking. QPL will help regional organisations to define or improve their business models. The aim is to make the new business models more environmentally friendly (e.g., more circular) but also economically sustainable. Wherever these support services help to implement new ideas that meet social needs, the measure can be considered social. Also, the current service contributes to the regional vision by increasing the number of regional actors that aim (and can support and participate) in the transition to a bioeconomy.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) QPL will identify some regional stakeholders that could benefit from its services and contact them to see if they are interested. 2) QPL will do some preparatory work to understand the organisation's activities and vision and will prepare a first draft of the business model canvas 3) QPL will invite a representative from the organisation to a meeting to ask them for more information and discuss the potential of turning the business model more circular. 4) QPL will prepare the final version of the business model canvas and share it with the beneficiary. 5) QPL will describe all its actions and outcomes in a short text that could be included in the ROBIN T3.2 deliverable.
Regional responsible	QPL
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	The business development support services are provided to 4-5 stakeholders.
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	The high quality of the service often depends on the availability of data and other information in the local or company context. We will perform dedicated interviews and/or ad hoc discussions with local actors to mitigate this risk.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	7) Development of communication material for local authorities and policymakers
Objective of the support action	To evaluate the local authority's knowledge of the bioeconomy and to promote awareness of the bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	The development of a cluster requires the definition of its activities and value proposition. One idea is to identify the needs, problems, and challenges that its members face and officially report them to policymakers. This will increase the visibility of the problems and needs leading potentially to more informed public policies that can accelerate the transition to bioeconomy.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) RCM will use the Policy monitoring tool and the Environmental protection planning tool to evaluate the baseline situation in the region. 2) RCM will develop communication material that could be used to contact and inform local authorities and policymakers. 3) RCM will utilise a variety of mediums such as written content, infographics, charts, and diagrams to convey complex information in a digestible format effectively. 4) Emphasis will be given to the importance of collaboration and engagement between local authorities, policymakers, and other relevant stakeholders.
Regional responsible	RCM
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Bioeconomy Awareness implemented /local authorities and Policymakers informed & engaged (8-10)
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	A social media campaign will support promotional efforts.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Policy monitoring tool Environmental protection planning tool

N°) Support action	8) Stakeholder engagement: local authorities
Objective of the support action	To evaluate the local authority's knowledge of the bioeconomy and to promote awareness of the bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	In line with the above, RCM will Identify relevant stakeholders within the local government structure (e.g., mayors, council members, city managers, and other key decision-makers.), establish clear communication lines and build trust and collaboration relationships with them. Also, it will organise a workshop where RCM will present the project and the material developed so far. Emphasis will be placed on the regional needs and challenges for the transition to bioeconomy that require the direct involvement of policymakers to be addressed. Then, RCM will discuss the idea of developing a bioeconomy cluster in Central Macedonia and ask them to provide input, share their expertise, and express their concerns. Finally, regular communication channels will be established to ensure that local authorities are aware of any developments, changes, or challenges that may arise to our plans.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) RCM/AUTH Identify regional needs and challenges for the transition to bioeconomy that require the direct involvement of policymakers to be addressed. 2) RCM/AUTH will discuss the idea of developing a bioeconomy cluster in Central Macedonia and ask them to provide input, share their expertise, and express their concerns. 3) Establish regular communication channels to ensure that local authorities are aware of any developments, changes, or challenges
Regional responsible	RCM/AUTH
Resources needed	Human Resources Financial resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	8-10 relevant stakeholders within the local government eager to participate and show will for collaboration.
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Clear communication and a specific engagement plan
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

Nº) Support action	9) Stakeholder engagement: academia
Objective of the support action	The primary goal of this action is to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange in RCM and local academic entities. By engaging with universities, colleges, research institutions, and scholars, the action aims to bridge the gap between industry and academia, promoting the dissemination of research, best practices, and innovative ideas. This engagement not only facilitates mutual learning but also seeks to identify areas of potential collaboration and contribution from academia to the bioeconomy cluster.
Description of the support action	Although a potential bioeconomy cluster in RCM would be constituted by industry actors, we aim to approach local academia, including universities, colleges, research institutions, and scholars. The reason is that stakeholder engagement with academia promotes knowledge transfer and exchange between academia and other stakeholders. It can facilitate the dissemination of research findings, best practices, and innovative ideas and fosters mutual learning. In practice, AUTH will list relevant academia stakeholders and invite them to a workshop. There, they will identify topics and requests from academia, elaborate on topics that are missing in the implementation of the bioeconomy, and discuss the potential contribution/collaboration of academia with the proposed bioeconomy cluster.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) AUTH will create a comprehensive list of relevant academic entities and scholars in Central Macedonia as well as organize the logistics, agenda, and materials required for the workshop. 2) AUTH will extend formal invitations to the identified academic stakeholders to attend the workshop. 3) During the workshop, AUTH will facilitate discussions on topics, requests, and potential gaps in the bioeconomy's implementation as well as guide the discussions towards the exploration of potential areas of contribution and collaboration between academia and the bioeconomy cluster. 4) Finally, AUTH will compile the findings, discussions, and potential action points from the workshop for future reference and action.
Regional responsible	AUTH
Resources needed	Financial Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 event held 5-10 stakeholders engaged
Potential risks	Low interest from the stakeholders to participate to the event
Corrective measures	Clear communication and a specific engagement plan/Reach out to all the Academic Institutes of Central Macedonia
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	It can provide insights for the policy monitoring tool and the environmental tool

Nº) Support action	10) Development of a regional bioeconomy cluster
Objective of the support action	The objective of this action is to set the grounds for the setup and operation of a region bioeconomy cluster in RCM, Greece.
Description of the support action	This action is the final step in our collective work to reach the vision co-created previously, to develop a regional cluster that could facilitate the collaboration among local bioeconomy actors and accelerate the transition to the bioeconomy. It involves bringing together various industry actors, including producers, intermediaries, consultancies, investors, service providers, etc., to discuss the potential of creating a bioeconomy cluster. Discussions on the cluster may include topics such as the potential cluster members, the key cluster activities, the governance structure and the decision-making processes, the revenue model and plans for the financial sustainability of the cluster, etc. Of course, the creation and operation of the cluster are beyond the scope of the ROBIN project, and it depends on the will of the regional actors and the regional circumstances. However, what can be done at this point is to (i) create important supportive materials, such as a mapping of the stakeholders and the description of the cluster services, and (ii) invite regional actors to discuss and potentially decide and commit to developing the cluster.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Collection and integration of knowledge and materials developed previously as a result of the regional analysis measures and social measures. 2) Mapping of bioeconomy industry actors in RCM and contacting them to invite them to a co-creation workshop where the opportunity to create a local bioeconomy cluster is discussed. 3) During the workshop, QPL presents the key project findings to help participants understand the current situation and the political and business context. Afterwards, QPL explains why participating in such a cluster would be valuable and presents the material that has been developed to support the development of the cluster (analysis of biomass resources and regional funding mechanisms, bioeconomy good practices, bioeconomy research infrastructures, business support services, and communication material). Finally, participants are invited to participate in a constructive discussion about the potential to develop such a cluster and potentially commonly agree on a set of actions and a timeline to this end. The exact mode (online/offline) of the workshop, as well as the participants, will be specified in due time depending on the availability of resources and the ability to achieve synergies with other projects/ initiatives. 4) Reporting on support action outcomes in ROBIN T3.2.
Regional responsible	QPL
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	It aims to bring on board as many as possible local actors (at least 10), organise structured dialogue among them (at least 1 meeting)

	and develop all preparatory material for the development of such a cluster.
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	We will utilise the network of QPL, RCM and AUTH and make direct contacts to ensure that at least a minimum number of key stakeholders will participate.
Linkages with other support actions	N/A
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC

Southern Region of Ireland (Ireland)

REGIONAL VISION/VALUE PROPOSITION:

Working Document to inform Regional Circular Bioeconomy & Structures

HOW THE ACTION PLAN AS A WHOLE DRIVES THE REGIONAL VISION FORWARD (FROM THE CO-CREATED GOVERNANCE MODEL):

Each action is a key component/chapter of a potential working strategy for the Southern Region. It provides a foundation for the future development of a Southern Region Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, allowing to map existing bioeconomy networks and activities already underway in the region and involving/mobilising key stakeholders.

Nº) Support action	1) Identification of relevant Bioeconomy Stakeholders in the region
Objective of the support action	Evaluate the stakeholders in the bioeconomy to seek out what resources and connections are available within the region.
Description of the support action	Create a map to highlight bioeconomy stakeholders within the region.
Steps of the support action	1) Begin researching bioeconomy stakeholders in the Southern Region of Ireland 2) Create a GIS (geographical information system) using this information
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Creation of Map
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Effective project management
Linkages with other support actions	2,3,4,5,6,7,8
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

N°) Support action	2) Establish Advisory Board
Objective of the support action	To gather academics, policy makers, civil society and industry actors to contribute their expertise towards our working document.
Description of the support action	Engage Quadruple Helix stakeholders to join the board and to collaborate on working document.
Steps of the support action	1) Reach out to our selected stakeholders to invite them to collaborate 2) Invite them to a bi-annual meeting 3) Invite them to provide feedback and access to networks
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Engage 5 board members, to meet twice a year
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Clear communication and a specific engagement plan
Linkages with other support actions	1,5,6,7,8,9,10
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

N°) Support action	3) Engage with Local Authorities
Objective of the support action	To evaluate the local authority's knowledge of the bioeconomy and to promote awareness of the bioeconomy.
Description of the support action	Reach out to local authorities to review their current levels of knowledge of the bioeconomy and to identify gaps (in engagement).
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Engage with Local Authorities 2) Assess their current knowledge of the bioeconomy using Mentimeter 3) Understand the current supports in place/required supports needed for bioeconomy development in local authorities 4) Host an event to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing of the bioeconomy
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	6 Mentimeter(or surveys) responses for Local Authorities
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Consistent Communication
Linkages with other support actions	1,4,6,7,8
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

N°) Support action	4) Bioeconomy Awareness Raising
Objective of the support action	To enhance awareness of the bioeconomy among stakeholders, including communities, cities and regions.
Description of the support action	Advancing bioeconomy awareness (inc. interaction with Bioeconomy Ireland Week).
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Host Launch event of Bioeconomy Ireland Week 2023 2) Invite stakeholders from communities, cities and regions in Ireland 3) Facilitate knowledge sharing of bioeconomy initiatives and coordinate a co-creation workshop 4) Disseminating best practice from ROBIN project
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Bioeconomy Awareness event at Irish Bioeconomy Week
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Defined and targeted action plan
Linkages with other support actions	3,1,6,7,8
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

N°) Support action	5) Education Mapping
Objective of the support action	To identify what education and skills are currently available that contribute to bioeconomy regional development.
Description of the support action	Review of bioeconomy higher education landscape in the region.
Steps of the support action	1) Map out available education courses /opportunities/ skills etc 2) Utilize these research findings to help identify gaps
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Review completed/Chapter delivered
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Effective project management
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,6
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

N°) Support action	6) Highlighting regional Bioeconomy Innovation
Objective of the support action	Highlighting Bioeconomy Research demonstration and commercial innovations in the Southern Region.
Description of the support action	Identifying bioeconomy activities underway within research and industrial environments in the region.
Steps of the support action	1) Identification of regional bioeconomy innovations 2) Identification of stakeholders involved 3) Identification of opportunity areas and research gaps
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Review completed/Chapter delivered
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Effective project management
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,3,4,5
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

N°) Support action	7) Biomass quantification
Objective of the support action	To map relevant regional biomass arisings for bioeconomy development.
Description of the support action	To understand the availability of biomass and side streams in the southern region.
Steps of the support action	1) Identify selected feedstocks for study 2) Map arisings of feedstock in the region
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Review completed/Chapter delivered
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Effective project management
Linkages with other support actions	Activity 1,2
ROBIN tool/s	Environmental Protection Tool

N°) Support action	8) Bioeconomy Funding assist
Objective of the support action	To explore accessible funding for bioeconomy research/implementation and highlight underutilized and beneficial funds for stakeholders in the Southern Region.
Description of the support action	Review of funding mechanisms (regional, national, EU level) and highlight underutilized ones.
Steps of the support action	1) Identify available funding for bioeconomy initiatives 2) Examine underutilized funds 3) Spotlight 5 funding mechanisms for the Southern Region
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Spotlight 5 funding mechanisms
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Defined research methodology
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,3,4
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform

N°) Support action	9) Evaluate Governance Structures and policies
Objective of the support action	Assess the most suitable governance structures and policies for the Southern Region.
Description of the support action	Review suitable governance structures and policies for Southern Region (Build on D1.2 and D1.3)
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Review D1.2 and D1.3 2) Assessment of governance structures and policies in the deliverables 3) Propose the most suitable governance structures and policies for the Southern Region
Regional responsible	SRA/MT
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Select the most suitable Governance structures and policy examples for the Southern Region
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Defined research methodology
Linkages with other support actions	10
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge Platform/ Typology Matrix

Nº) Support action	10) Examination of existing policies, strategies currently influencing and/or effecting the circular bioeconomy in the region
Objective of the support action	Evaluate what policies/strategies influence the bioeconomy in the Southern Region.
Description of the support action	Examination of current policy/strategy application at Nuts1/Nuts2/Nuts3 (eg. Environmental policies, waste management plans, RSES etc.)
Steps of the support action	1) Identify all relevant strategies/policies 2) Assess the influence on the bioeconomy in the southern region 3) Assess relevant information to be incorporated into our working document
Regional responsible	SRA/MTU
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Review completed/Chapter delivered
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Defined research methodology
Linkages with other support actions	9,2,3
ROBIN tool/s	N/A

Zilina (Czech Republic)

REGIONAL VISION/VALUE PROPOSITION:

A system of rational land use based on the principles of circular bioeconomy. One of the main actions defined in the Economic and social development programme is the Creation of Regional Circular Centres.

HOW THE ACTION PLAN AS A WHOLE DRIVES THE REGIONAL VISION FORWARD (FROM THE CO-CREATED GOVERNANCE MODEL):

Each action is a key component/chapter of a potential working strategy for the Southern Region. It provides with a foundation for the future development of a Southern Region Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, allowing to map existing bioeconomy networks and activities already underway in the region and involving/mobilising key stakeholders.

Nº) Support action	1) Identification of biomass sources availability and potential
Objective of the support action	Analysis of the region focused on biomass sources availability and potential application in the region.
Description of the support action	Identification of biomass sources availability and potential
Steps of the support action	1) Identify resources needed to conduct the analysis 2) Define the scope 3) Coordination of the analysis 4) Results will be presented and discussed with a group of key actors and stakeholders
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Human resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 analysis / nº of resources identified
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Proper planning and preparation of the action, including the scope of the action, dedicating resources, consistent communication, and monitoring of the progress of the action
Linkages with other support actions	2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10
ROBIN tool/s	Environmental protection tool

N°) Support action	2) Identification of key actors in the region - project promoters - change agents
Objective of the support action	To define target groups which are relevant in the bioeconomy sector. The expected result is a stakeholders analysis based on the "power" and "interest" criteria.
Description of the support action	Create a map highlighting bioeconomy stakeholders within the region.
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify resources needed to conduct the analysis 2) Define the scope 3) Coordination of the analysis 4) Results will be presented and discussed with a group of key actors and stakeholders
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Human resources
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 list of stakeholders created
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Proper planning and preparation of the action, including the scope of the action, dedicating resources, consistent communication and monitoring of the progress of the action.
Linkages with other support actions	1,3,4,6
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC Support Action Portfolio

Nº) Support action	3) Analyse the current priorities, needs and activities of Local Action Groups (LEADER Programme) and potential for further development
Objective of the support action	Discussion with the LAGs in order to exchange information and experiences with LAGs, with the aim to identify priorities, needs and activities of Local Action Groups, based on which the potential pilot actions plan can be developed.
Description of the support action	Reach out to existing LAGs to review their current levels of knowledge of the bioeconomy and regional development and to identify gaps (active role in development)
Steps of the support action	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify resources needed to conduct the analysis 2) Define the scope 3) Coordination of the analysis 4) Results will be presented and discussed with a group of key actors and stakeholders
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 document with activities identified.
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Careful preparation, including key actors to be involved, the content to be discussed, preliminary identification of the priorities, timely and consistent communication.
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,4,6
ROBIN tool/s	Policy monitoring tool CBGMC

N°) Support action	4) Identifying examples of good and bad practice from Slovakia
Objective of the support action	Identify and analyse effective and inspiring bioeconomy practices from other regions to be presented to the regional actors.
Description of the support action	Identify matchmaking opportunities and successful case studies.
Steps of the support action	1) Identify resources needed to conduct the analysis 2) Define the scope 3) Coordination of the analysis 4) Results will be presented and discussed with a group of key actors and stakeholders"
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Short term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 document summarizing good and best practices
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Proper planning and preparation of the action, including the scope of the action, dedicating resources, consistent communication and monitoring of the progress of the action.
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,3
ROBIN tool/s	Knowledge platform

N°) Support action	5) Analysis of funding opportunities to finance measures in the field of bioeconomy development
Objective of the support action	In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union. The objective here is to identify the possibilities of existing financing schemes (at the national, macro-regional, European level) that can be utilized to fund regional activities.
Description of the support action	Map and create a list of relevant funding schemes (national, macro-regional, European) in the current programming period that could be used to finance implementation of pilot actions
Steps of the support action	1) Identify resources needed to conduct the analysis 2) Define the scope 3) Coordination of the analysis 4) Results will be presented and discussed with a group of key actors and stakeholders"
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Long term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Planning process defined (who, how...)
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Proper planning and preparation of the action, including the scope of the action, dedicating resources, consistent communication and effective project management.
Linkages with other support actions	4,6,7,8,9,10
ROBIN tool/s	Typology Matrix Support Action Portfolio

N°) Support action	6) Communication, involvement, developing relationships with actors, networking
Objective of the support action	To promote networking activities among the key actors in the region.
Description of the support action	Support of bioeconomy through social networks and involving the general public (including young people) in discussions.
Steps of the support action	1) Organize a workshop with key actors and stakeholders to present and discuss the results of step 0-2 2) Define potential pilot activities (pool of activities to be further discussed based on existing resources)
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Data and Information
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 stakeholders engagement plan
Potential risks	Stakeholder Engagement Risks
Corrective measures	Careful preparation, including key actors to be involved, the content to be discussed, preliminary identification of the priorities, timely and consistent communication.
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,3,4,5,7,8,9,10
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC Support Action Portfolio

Nº) Support action	7) Developing a plan for pilot actions and their implementation, incl. identification of the needs of key areas in the bioeconomy and possible cooperation
Objective of the support action	Analysis of pilot actions suitable for implementation in the region.
Description of the support action	Analysis of the region's needs and development of pilot actions suitable for the region
Steps of the support action	1) Identify potential for collaboration (where activities and funding could be directed) 2) Prioritisation
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 pilot actions plan developed
Potential risks	Socioeconomic Risks
Corrective measures	Proper planning and preparation of the action, including the scope of the action, dedicating resources, consistent communication and effective project management.
Linkages with other support actions	4,5,6,8
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC Support Action Portfolio

N°) Support action	8) Definition of needs focusing on capacity building in the region in specific areas
Objective of the support action	Analysis of the gaps in knowledge/skills/competences and the possibilities of capacity building in the field of bioeconomy in the region (including potential providers).
Description of the support action	Analysis of needs and educational opportunities in the field of bioeconomy and study of examples of good practice
Steps of the support action	1) During the workshop, priority areas of capacity building will be identified. 2) Based on that, a plan of capacity building activities will be developed.
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 map of educational activities
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Proper planning and preparation of the action, including the scope of the action, dedicating resources, consistent communication and effective project management
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,3,4,5,6
ROBIN tool/s	CBGMC Support Action Portfolio

N°) Support action	9) Implementation of awareness raising and education activities
Objective of the support action	Advancing bioeconomy awareness of different target groups, including youth.
Description of the support action	Review of bioeconomy education landscape in the region and developing a plan of awareness raising and education activities.
Steps of the support action	1) Plan of events analysed and opportunities to cover bioeconomy will be identified. 2) Initial awareness raising activities focusing on youth and general public implemented.
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Financial Resources
Time frame	Long term
Success Criteria/ KPI	1 plan of awareness raising and education activities
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Identification of key target groups to be addressed, development of a plan of awareness raising and educational actions, identification of resources and partners, effective project management.
Linkages with other support actions	2,4,6,8
ROBIN tool/s	Support Action Portfolio

N°) Support action	10) Monitoring and evaluation tools and processes
Objective of the support action	Identify monitoring and evaluation tools and processes
Description of the support action	Design a monitoring and evaluation processes and tools
Steps of the support action	1) Workshop presenting ROBIN tools (Policy monitoring and Environmental Protection Plan) to key actor.
Regional responsible	RA ŽSK/PEDAL
Resources needed	Human Resources
Time frame	Medium term
Success Criteria/ KPI	Monitoring and evaluation process described (who, how...)
Potential risks	Implementation Risks
Corrective measures	Careful assessment of the region's needs and internal processes, presentation and internal training
Linkages with other support actions	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9
ROBIN tool/s	Policy monitoring tool Support Action Portfolio

5. Conclusions

The work developed within task 2.2. during the 12 months it lasted (M5-M16 of the ROBIN project) allowed the regions to obtain a detailed Regional Action Plan with 10 dedicated Support Actions each oriented towards the consecution of the Regional Vision/Value Proposition identified as most important by the project partners and the MARC members of each region during the co-creation workshops implemented in task 2.1.

For the design of these Regional Action Plans, four dedicated support materials were also provided:

- The ROBIN Support Action Portfolio, acting as an inspirational element with an extensive list of measures that could be included as support actions in the Regional Action Plan;
- The ROBIN Regional Action Plan template, with structured fields in order to help the regions to clearly identify the most relevant information of each support action included in the Regional Action Plans;
- The ROBIN Action Plans Workshop, held in Cork on the 4th of October and focused as a cross-fertilization activity among regions and an opportunity to finetune the regional drafts of the Regional Action Plan;
- The Plan-Do-Check-Act methodology as a tool for the evaluation of the implementation of the Regional Action Plans and the design of the validation activity under WP3.

As a general overview of the 5 Regional Action Plans development, results and KPIs, the table below contents the main figures:

Table 4. RAPs results and KPIs

	REGIONAL ACTION PLAN	SUPPORT ACTIONS	SOCIAL MEASURES	ROBIN TOOLS							TOOLS PER REGION
				SAP	KP	CBGMC	ET	PMT	TM	N/A	
AND	1	10	3	4	1	3	0	2	0	1	10
BW	1	10	4	3	2	4	0	0	0	1	9
RCM	1	10	5	0	6	1	3	1	0	0	11
SRI	1	10	3	0	3	0	1	0	1	6	5
ZIL	1	10	2	7	1	5	1	2	1	0	17
TOTAL	5	50	17	14	13	13	5	5	2	8	52

Going into detail about the social measures included per region, can be specifically found listed below:

Table 5. Social measures included per RAP

AND	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA2. Awareness raising about circular bioeconomy potential as study field and job career among young and students. • SA3. Networking activities among all relevant regional, national and international stakeholders. • SA9. Development of communication plan to increase awareness about circular bioeconomy.
BW	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA4. Define target groups in the bioeconomy sector. • SA5. Identification of gaps in the education sector related to the bioeconomy. • SA6. Identification of gaps in the communication material for civil society. • SA9. Thematic exchange with other federal states of Germany
RCM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA1. Networking activities among relevant regional stakeholders. • SA5. Development of communication material for local authorities and policymakers. • SA6. Business support and social entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy remit. • SA8. Stakeholder engagement: local authorities. • SA9. Stakeholder engagement: academia.
SRI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA2. Establish Advisory Board • SA3. Engage with Local Authorities • SA4. Bioeconomy Awareness Raising
ZILINA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SA6. Communication, involvement, developing relationships with actors, networking. • SA9. Implementation of awareness raising and education activities.

The results of T2.2. are directly contributing to the following projects KPI:

- KPI-6: Support actions for the development or update of regional / local strategies:
 - Target value: ≈ 50
 - Result obtained: a total of 50 support actions are included in the 5 Regional Action Plans
- KPI-9: New business models and social measures co-created:
 - Target value: > 10
 - Result obtained:
 - 17 social measures included as support actions in the Regional Action Plans.
 - 1 support action aiming at developing a business model (RCM SA6. “Business support and social entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy remit”)
- Coordination support actions:
 - Target value: > 10
 - Result obtained: 49 coordination support actions included in the Support Action Portfolio

6. References

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7. Annex 1. Support Actions Portfolio

Title	Identification of relevant actors/project promoters/change agents at regional level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM1
Description of the support action	<p>Identification of relevant actors or project promoters or change agents is a crucial step in any action or initiative. These individuals or organizations play a significant role in driving and implementing change, and their involvement is essential for the success of any project.</p> <p>The process of identifying relevant actors or project promoters begins with a thorough analysis of the project's objectives, goals, and scope. This analysis helps in understanding the key stakeholders who will be affected by or have an interest in the project. These stakeholders can include individuals, organizations, or even communities.</p> <p>Once the stakeholders are identified, the next step is to assess their level of influence, power, and interest in the project. This assessment helps in prioritizing the stakeholders and determining their potential role in driving the desired change. It is important to consider both formal and informal actors, as sometimes the most influential individuals or organizations may not hold official positions.</p> <p>In addition to assessing influence and interest, it is also crucial to consider the expertise and resources that the identified actors or project promoters can bring to the table. Their knowledge, skills, and networks can greatly contribute to the successful implementation of the project.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ANDALUCIA ZILINA

Title	Identification of educational offer in bioeconomy at regional level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM2
Description of the support action	<p>This action aims to gather information on the various educational programs, courses, and training opportunities available in the bioeconomy sector within a specific region.</p> <p>The process begins with extensive research and data collection from educational institutions, universities, research centres, and other relevant stakeholders in the region. This includes gathering information on undergraduate and postgraduate programs, vocational training courses, workshops, and seminars that focus on bioeconomy-related subjects.</p> <p>The collected data is then organized and analysed to create a comprehensive database of the educational offerings in the bioeconomy sector. This database includes details such as the name of the educational institution, program/course title, duration, admission requirements, curriculum, and any additional information that may be relevant for prospective students or individuals interested in expanding their knowledge in the field.</p> <p>The identification of the educational offer in bioeconomy at the regional level serves multiple purposes. Firstly, it provides a valuable resource for individuals who are interested in pursuing a career or further education in the bioeconomy sector. They can easily access information on the available programs and make informed decisions about their educational path.</p> <p>Secondly, it helps educational institutions and stakeholders in the region to understand the existing educational landscape in the bioeconomy sector. This information can be used to identify gaps in the current offerings and develop new programs or courses to meet the growing demand for skilled professionals in the field.</p> <p>Furthermore, the identification of the educational offer in bioeconomy at the regional level can also serve as a basis for collaboration and networking among educational institutions, researchers, and industry professionals. It facilitates the exchange of knowledge, resources, and best practices, ultimately contributing to the overall development and advancement of the bioeconomy sector in the region.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUCIA</p> <p>BADEN WUERTTEMBERG</p> <p>SOUTHER REGION OF IRELAND</p>

Title	Analysis of biomass resources and potential
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM3
Description of the support action	<p>This action involves gathering and examining data on various sources of biomass, such as agricultural residues, forestry waste, and energy crops, to determine their availability and suitability for different applications.</p> <p>The first step in this process is to collect data on the quantity and quality of biomass resources in a given region. This may involve conducting surveys, consulting existing databases, and collaborating with relevant stakeholders such as farmers, foresters, and energy companies. The collected data is then analysed to identify the most abundant and accessible biomass resources.</p> <p>Next, the analysis focuses on assessing the potential of these resources for different uses. This includes evaluating their energy content, moisture content, and chemical composition to determine their suitability for conversion into biofuels, biogas, or other forms of renewable energy. The analysis also considers factors such as transportation logistics, infrastructure requirements, and environmental impacts to identify the most viable options for biomass utilization.</p> <p>In addition to energy production, the analysis may also explore other potential applications of biomass resources. For example, certain types of biomasses may be suitable for the production of bio-based materials, such as bioplastics or biochar, which can help reduce reliance on fossil fuels and mitigate climate change.</p> <p>The output of this analysis is a comprehensive report that provides insights into the biomass resources available in a specific region and their potential for various applications. This information can be used by policymakers, investors, and other stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding the development of biomass-based industries and the implementation of sustainable energy strategies.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUCIA</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p> <p>ZILINA</p>

Title	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at governance level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM4
Description of the support action	<p>The analysis of barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at the governance level aims to identify and understand the challenges and obstacles that hinder the successful implementation and growth of the bioeconomy.</p> <p>At the governance level, various factors can impede the development of the bioeconomy. One significant barrier is the lack of supportive policies and regulations. In many cases, existing policies and regulations are outdated or not tailored to the specific needs and characteristics of the bioeconomy. This can create uncertainty and discourage investments in bio-based industries. Additionally, conflicting policies and regulations across different sectors and levels of government can create confusion and hinder the coordination necessary for the bioeconomy's success.</p> <p>Another barrier is the limited availability of funding and financial incentives. The bioeconomy requires significant investments in research and development, infrastructure, and market development. However, funding sources for bio-based projects are often limited, and financial incentives may not be sufficient to attract private sector investments. This lack of financial support can slow down the deployment of the bioeconomy and limit its potential for economic growth and job creation.</p> <p>Furthermore, the lack of awareness and understanding of the bioeconomy among policymakers and stakeholders can be a significant barrier. Many decision-makers may not fully grasp the potential benefits and opportunities offered by the bioeconomy, leading to a lack of political will and support. This can result in a lack of prioritization and inadequate allocation of resources for bio-based initiatives.</p> <p>Lastly, the complexity and fragmentation of governance structures can hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy. The bioeconomy involves multiple sectors, including agriculture, forestry, energy, and waste management, which are often governed by different authorities and institutions. This fragmentation can lead to a lack of coordination and collaboration, making it challenging to develop integrated policies and strategies for the bioeconomy.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

<p>Title</p>	<p>Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at technical level</p>
<p>Type of support action</p>	<p>Regional Analysis Measure</p>
<p>Code</p>	<p>RM5</p>
<p>Description of the support action</p>	<p>The analysis of barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at a technical level aims to identify and understand the challenges and obstacles that hinder the widespread adoption and implementation of bio-based technologies and processes.</p> <p>One of the main barriers identified is the lack of technological readiness and maturity of bio-based processes and technologies. Many bio-based solutions are still in the early stages of development and face technical challenges such as low efficiency, high costs, and limited scalability. This hinders their commercial viability and widespread adoption by industries.</p> <p>Another barrier is the limited availability and accessibility of feedstock. Bio-based processes rely on the availability of biomass, which can be derived from various sources such as agricultural residues, forestry waste, and algae. However, the availability and quality of these feedstocks can vary geographically and seasonally, making it challenging to ensure a consistent and reliable supply.</p> <p>Furthermore, the integration of bio-based processes into existing industrial infrastructures poses technical challenges. Retrofitting existing facilities to accommodate bio-based technologies can be complex and costly. Additionally, the compatibility and interoperability of bio-based processes with existing systems and equipment need to be addressed to ensure smooth integration.</p> <p>The lack of standardized and harmonized regulations and policies is another barrier to the deployment of the bioeconomy at a technical level. Unclear or inconsistent regulations can create uncertainties and hinder investments in bio-based technologies. Additionally, the absence of clear sustainability criteria and certification schemes for bio-based products can make it difficult for consumers and industries to make informed choices.</p> <p>To overcome these barriers, collaboration and knowledge-sharing among stakeholders are crucial. Public-private partnerships, research collaborations, and knowledge exchange platforms can facilitate the development and deployment of bio-based technologies. Additionally, targeted funding and incentives can encourage investments in research and development, as well as the adoption of bio-based solutions.</p>
<p>ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP</p>	<p>ANDALUCIA CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p>

Title	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at legal and normative level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM6
Description of the support action	<p>The task involves conducting an analysis of the barriers that hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy at the legal and normative level.</p> <p>To begin the analysis, a comprehensive review of existing laws, regulations, and norms related to the bioeconomy will be conducted. This will involve examining national, regional, and international legal frameworks that govern the production, trade, and use of biological resources. The objective is to identify any legal barriers or inconsistencies that impede the development and expansion of the bioeconomy.</p> <p>Additionally, the analysis will assess the effectiveness and adequacy of existing norms and standards in promoting the bioeconomy. This will involve evaluating the compatibility of current norms with the principles and objectives of the bioeconomy, such as sustainability, circularity, and resource efficiency. Any gaps or limitations in the existing normative frameworks will be identified and addressed.</p> <p>Furthermore, the analysis will explore the potential conflicts or contradictions between different legal and normative instruments that may hinder the deployment of the bioeconomy. This could include conflicts between environmental regulations and agricultural policies, or inconsistencies between international trade agreements and domestic bioeconomy strategies. Recommendations will be provided to reconcile these conflicts and ensure coherence and synergy among different legal and normative instruments.</p> <p>The findings of the analysis will be used to develop strategies and policy recommendations to overcome the identified barriers. These recommendations may include the revision or development of new laws and regulations, the establishment of supportive policy frameworks, and the promotion of international cooperation and harmonization. The aim is to create an enabling environment that facilitates the deployment of the bioeconomy, encourages investment and innovation, and fosters sustainable economic development.</p> <p>Overall, this analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at the legal and normative level will provide valuable insights and guidance for policymakers, stakeholders, and decision-makers to promote the transition towards a more sustainable and bio-based economy.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the support action	-

Title	Analysis of the barriers for the deployment of the bioeconomy at end-user level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM7
Description of the support action	<p>The analysis of barriers to the deployment of the bioeconomy at the end-user level aims to identify and understand the challenges and obstacles that hinder the widespread adoption and implementation of bio-based products and processes by end-users.</p> <p>One of the main barriers identified is the lack of awareness and understanding among end-users about the benefits and potential of bio-based products. Many end-users are not familiar with the concept of the bioeconomy and are unaware of the environmental and economic advantages it offers. This lack of awareness often leads to a preference for traditional, non-bio-based products, which hinders the growth and development of the bioeconomy.</p> <p>Another significant barrier is the limited availability and accessibility of bio-based products. End-users often face challenges in finding and accessing a wide range of bio-based alternatives to traditional products. This limited availability is due to various factors, including the high costs of production and the lack of infrastructure for the production and distribution of bio-based products.</p> <p>Additionally, regulatory barriers pose a challenge to the deployment of the bioeconomy at the end-user level. The complex and fragmented regulatory landscape surrounding bio-based products often creates uncertainty and confusion among end-users. This uncertainty can deter end-users from adopting bio-based products, as they may be unsure about compliance requirements and potential risks.</p> <p>Furthermore, the lack of supportive policies and incentives for the bioeconomy is a significant barrier. End-users may be hesitant to invest in bio-based products and processes without clear and favourable policies that promote their adoption. The absence of financial incentives and supportive frameworks can hinder the growth and development of the bioeconomy.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Analysis of relevant regional strategies and legislation
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM8
Description of the support action	<p>A comprehensive analysis of relevant regional strategies and legislation is conducted to provide valuable insights and guidance for decision-making and policy development. This process involves examining the various strategies and legislation implemented by different regions to address specific issues or achieve certain goals.</p> <p>The analysis begins by identifying the key regional strategies and legislation that are relevant to the specific context or problem at hand. This may include policies related to economic development, environmental protection, social welfare, or any other area of concern. The identified strategies and legislation are then thoroughly reviewed and evaluated to understand their objectives, scope, and effectiveness.</p> <p>The analysis also involves assessing the implementation and enforcement of these strategies and legislation in different regions. This includes examining the resources allocated, the mechanisms in place for monitoring and evaluation, and the level of compliance and enforcement. By understanding the strengths and weaknesses of the implementation process, recommendations can be made to improve the effectiveness of regional strategies and legislation.</p> <p>Furthermore, the analysis explores the impact and outcomes of these strategies and legislation on the regions where they have been implemented. This includes evaluating the extent to which the desired goals and objectives have been achieved, as well as any unintended consequences or challenges that have arisen. By examining the outcomes, valuable lessons can be learned and shared to inform future policy development and decision-making.</p> <p>The findings of the analysis are then synthesized and presented in a comprehensive report or presentation. This includes highlighting the key insights and recommendations derived from the analysis, as well as providing a clear overview of the regional strategies and legislation that have been examined. The report serves as a valuable resource for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders, providing them with a deeper understanding of the regional strategies and legislation that have been successful in addressing specific issues or achieving desired outcomes.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUCIA</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p>

Title	Regional bioeconomy strategy analysis
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM9
Description of the support action	<p>The regional bioeconomy strategy analysis is a comprehensive examination of the bioeconomy sector within a specific region. This analysis aims to assess the current state of the bioeconomy, identify opportunities for growth and development, and provide strategic recommendations for maximizing the region's bioeconomy potential.</p> <p>The analysis begins by gathering data and information on the region's bioeconomy, including the types of bio-based industries present, the scale of their operations, and the economic impact they have on the region. This data is then analysed to understand the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats facing the bioeconomy sector.</p> <p>The analysis also considers the region's natural resources and their potential for bio-based production. This includes evaluating the availability of biomass feedstocks, such as agricultural residues, forestry waste, and algae, and assessing their suitability for various bio-based applications. Additionally, the analysis examines the region's existing infrastructure, such as research institutions, innovation hubs, and transportation networks, to determine their capacity to support bioeconomy growth.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the support action	<p>ANDALUCIA</p> <p>BADEN WUERTEMBERG</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p>

Title	Implementation of regional bioeconomy strategy analysis
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM10
Description of the support action	<p>The implementation of a regional bioeconomy strategy analysis involves a comprehensive examination and evaluation of the potential for developing and utilizing bio-based resources within a specific region. This analysis aims to identify and assess the various opportunities and challenges associated with the bioeconomy sector, with the ultimate goal of promoting sustainable economic growth and environmental stewardship.</p> <p>The first step in this process is to gather relevant data and information about the region's existing bio-based resources, such as agricultural crops, forestry products, and waste materials. This data is then analyzed to determine the potential for converting these resources into value-added products and services, such as biofuels, bioplastics, and bio-based chemicals.</p> <p>The analysis also takes into consideration the region's existing infrastructure and capabilities, including research and development facilities, manufacturing capacity, and transportation networks. This assessment helps to identify any gaps or limitations that may need to be addressed in order to fully capitalize on the bioeconomy potential.</p> <p>Furthermore, the analysis examines the market demand and potential for bio-based products and services within the region, as well as in neighbouring markets. This includes assessing the current and projected market size, consumer preferences, and regulatory frameworks that may impact the development and commercialization of bio-based products.</p> <p>Based on the findings of the analysis, a regional bioeconomy strategy is developed, outlining the key objectives, targets, and actions needed to promote the growth of the bioeconomy sector. This strategy may include recommendations for policy and regulatory changes, investment in research and development, infrastructure development, and capacity building initiatives.</p> <p>The implementation of the strategy involves collaboration and coordination among various stakeholders, including government agencies, industry associations, research institutions, and local communities. It requires a multi-disciplinary approach, bringing together expertise from fields such as agriculture, forestry, chemistry, engineering, and economics.</p> <p>Overall, the implementation of a regional bioeconomy strategy analysis is a crucial step towards harnessing the potential of bio-based resources for sustainable economic development, job creation, and environmental protection. It provides a roadmap for policymakers and stakeholders to navigate the complex landscape of the bioeconomy sector and make informed decisions that will drive its growth and success.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Analysis of regional funding mechanisms and instruments (public level)
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM11
Description of the support action	<p>This analysis aims to provide a detailed understanding of the various ways in which regions are funded and the instruments used to allocate these funds.</p> <p>The analysis will begin by examining the different funding mechanisms that exist at the regional level. This will include an exploration of the sources of funding, such as government grants, taxes, and fees. The analysis will also consider the distribution of funds among regions and the criteria used to determine the allocation of resources.</p> <p>In addition to examining the funding mechanisms, the analysis will also delve into the instruments used to distribute these funds within regions. This will involve an exploration of the different programs and initiatives that are funded at the regional level, such as infrastructure development, education, healthcare, and social welfare. The analysis will assess the effectiveness of these instruments in achieving their intended goals and the impact they have on regional development.</p> <p>Furthermore, the analysis will consider the governance structures and decision-making processes that govern regional funding. This will involve an examination of the roles and responsibilities of different stakeholders, such as regional governments, central governments, and regional development agencies. The analysis will also assess the transparency and accountability of these processes to ensure that funds are being allocated in a fair and equitable manner.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUCIA</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>ZILINA</p>

Title	Analysis of regional financing opportunities (private initiatives)
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM12
Description of the support action	<p>The objective is to identify potential avenues for securing funding within a specific geographical area.</p> <p>To begin the analysis, a comprehensive review of the regional financial landscape will be conducted. This will involve examining the current economic conditions, market trends, and investment patterns within the region. By understanding the broader financial context, it will be possible to identify potential opportunities for private financing.</p> <p>Next, the analysis will delve into the specific private initiatives within the region. This will involve researching and evaluating various private sector projects, businesses, and organizations that are seeking financing. The aim is to identify those initiatives that align with the desired criteria and have the potential for successful funding.</p> <p>In addition to evaluating individual initiatives, the analysis will also consider the overall investment climate within the region. This will involve assessing the regulatory environment, government policies, and incentives that may impact private financing opportunities. By understanding the broader investment climate, it will be possible to identify any potential barriers or facilitators to securing funding.</p> <p>Furthermore, the analysis will explore various financing options available to private initiatives within the region. This may include traditional sources such as banks and financial institutions, as well as alternative financing options such as venture capital, angel investors, and crowdfunding platforms. By considering a range of financing options, the analysis aims to identify the most suitable and viable avenues for private initiatives.</p> <p>Finally, the analysis will culminate in the development of a comprehensive report outlining the regional financing opportunities for private initiatives. This report will provide a detailed overview of the potential funding sources, investment climate, and financing options available within the region. It will serve as a valuable resource for private initiatives seeking funding and will help guide decision-making processes.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the support action	<p>ANDALUSIA</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p>

Title	Identification of bioeconomy research infrastructures at regional level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM13
Description of the support action	<p>The objective of this action is to identify and map the bioeconomy research infrastructures available in different regions. This will help in understanding the existing capabilities and resources in the field of bioeconomy research at the regional level. The identification process will involve gathering information about the research facilities, laboratories, equipment, and expertise available in each region.</p> <p>The first step in this action is to collect data on the bioeconomy research infrastructures in each region. This can be done through surveys, interviews, and desk research. The collected data will include information about the type of infrastructure, its capacity, the research areas it focuses on, and the expertise available.</p> <p>Once the data is collected, it will be analysed to identify the strengths and weaknesses of each region in terms of bioeconomy research infrastructure. This analysis will help in identifying the areas where further investment and development are needed. It will also provide insights into the potential collaborations and partnerships that can be established between different regions.</p> <p>The output of this action will be a comprehensive report or database that lists the bioeconomy research infrastructures available in each region. This report will serve as a valuable resource for policymakers, researchers, and industry stakeholders who are interested in bioeconomy research and development. It will help them identify the available resources and expertise in different regions, facilitating collaboration and knowledge exchange.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ANDALUCIA CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Analysis of the use of the bioeconomy research infrastructures at regional level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM14
Description of the support action	<p>The analysis of the use of bioeconomy research infrastructures at the regional level aims to provide insights into the utilization and effectiveness of these facilities in promoting bioeconomic development. Bioeconomy research infrastructures refer to the physical and virtual resources, such as laboratories, databases, and networks, that support research and innovation in the field of bioeconomy.</p> <p>The analysis begins by collecting data on the bioeconomy research infrastructures available in a specific region. This includes identifying the types of infrastructures, their capacities, and the research areas they focus on. The data is then analysed to determine the extent to which these infrastructures are being utilized by researchers, industry professionals, and other stakeholders.</p> <p>The analysis also examines the impact of these infrastructures on regional bioeconomic development. This involves assessing the number and quality of research projects conducted using these infrastructures, as well as the level of collaboration between researchers, industry, and government agencies. The analysis also considers the extent to which these infrastructures have contributed to the development of new bio-based products, processes, and services.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Analysis of the existing bioeconomy governance structure in the region
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM15
Description of the support action	<p>The analysis will begin by examining the current governance framework in place for the bioeconomy. This will involve a thorough review of existing policies, regulations, and institutions that govern the bioeconomy at regional and national levels. The aim is to understand the strengths and weaknesses of the current governance structure and identify any gaps or areas for improvement.</p> <p>Key stakeholders involved in the bioeconomy, including government agencies, industry associations, research institutions, and civil society organizations, will be consulted to gather their perspectives on the governance structure. This will be done through interviews, surveys, and workshops to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the current situation.</p> <p>The analysis will also assess the effectiveness of the governance structure in achieving the objectives of the bioeconomy. This will involve evaluating the extent to which the current governance framework promotes sustainable practices, fosters innovation, and supports the growth of the bioeconomy. Additionally, the analysis will examine the inclusiveness and transparency of the governance structure, ensuring that all relevant stakeholders have a voice in decision-making processes.</p> <p>Based on the findings of the analysis, a set of recommendations will be developed to enhance the bioeconomy governance structure. These recommendations will aim to address any identified gaps or weaknesses and promote a more effective and inclusive governance framework. They may include suggestions for policy reforms, institutional changes, capacity building initiatives, and stakeholder engagement strategies.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUCIA</p> <p>BADEN WUERTTEMBERG</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p>

Title	Identification of bioeconomy good practices at regional level
Type of support action	Regional Analysis Measure
Code	RM16
Description of the support action	<p>The objective of this action is to identify and document bioeconomy good practices at the regional level.</p> <p>The first step of this action is to gather information on bioeconomy initiatives and projects that have been implemented at the regional level. This includes initiatives related to bio-based industries, sustainable agriculture, forestry, and fisheries, as well as bioenergy and biotechnology. Information is collected through desk research, interviews with key stakeholders, and surveys.</p> <p>Once the information is gathered, a thorough analysis is conducted to identify the most successful and innovative bioeconomy practices. These practices are evaluated based on their environmental, economic, and social impacts, as well as their potential for replication and scalability. The analysis also takes into account the specific regional context, including the availability of resources and the local market conditions.</p> <p>The identified good practices are then documented in a comprehensive report. The report provides detailed descriptions of each practice, including the objectives, activities, and outcomes. It also includes information on the key stakeholders involved, the funding sources, and any challenges or lessons learned during implementation.</p> <p>The report serves as a valuable resource for policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders interested in promoting the bioeconomy at the regional level. It provides concrete examples of successful initiatives that can be replicated or adapted to other regions. The report also highlights the potential of the bioeconomy to contribute to sustainable development goals, such as climate change mitigation, biodiversity conservation, and rural development.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>BADEN WUERTTEMBERG</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p> <p>ZILINA</p>

Title	Development of a bioeconomy awareness raising strategy
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM1
Description of the support action	<p>This activity involves creating a comprehensive plan to educate and engage stakeholders about the benefits and potential of a bio-based economy. This plan should include the identification of objectives, target audiences, key messages, communication channels, and evaluating the impact of the strategy. The first step in developing this strategy is to conduct a thorough analysis of the current state of awareness and understanding of the bioeconomy. This will involve reviewing existing literature, conducting surveys and interviews, and engaging with experts in the field. By understanding the existing knowledge gaps and misconceptions, we can tailor our awareness-raising efforts to address these specific areas.</p> <p>Based on the findings of the analysis, the strategy will outline a range of activities and initiatives to increase awareness and understanding of the bioeconomy. These may include educational campaigns targeting schools and universities, public awareness campaigns through various media channels, and workshops and seminars for policymakers and industry leaders.</p> <p>One key aspect of the strategy will be to highlight the economic and environmental benefits of the bioeconomy. This will involve showcasing successful case studies and examples of how the bioeconomy has contributed to job creation, economic growth, and the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions. By demonstrating the tangible benefits, we can generate interest and support for the bioeconomy among various stakeholders.</p> <p>Another important component of the strategy will be to address any potential concerns or misconceptions about the bioeconomy. This may involve providing accurate and evidence-based information about the safety and sustainability of bio-based products and processes. It will also involve engaging with stakeholders and addressing their concerns through open dialogue and transparent communication.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ANDALUSIA BADEN WUERTTEMBERG SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND ZILINA

Title	Stakeholder engagement: local authorities
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM2
Description of the support action	<p>The process of engaging local authorities begins with identifying and mapping out the relevant stakeholders within the local government structure. This includes mayors, council members, city managers, and other key decision-makers. It is important to establish clear lines of communication and build relationships with these individuals to foster trust and collaboration.</p> <p>Once the stakeholders have been identified, the next step is to actively involve them in the decision-making process. This can be done through regular meetings, workshops, or consultations where local authorities are given the opportunity to provide input, share their expertise, and express their concerns. These engagements should be inclusive and transparent, allowing for open dialogue and the exchange of ideas.</p> <p>Engaging local authorities as stakeholders also involves keeping them informed and updated on the progress of the project or decision. Regular communication channels should be established to ensure that local authorities are aware of any developments, changes, or challenges that may arise. This helps to maintain their engagement and ensures that they remain invested in the process.</p> <p>Overall, engaging local authorities as stakeholders is essential for effective governance and decision-making. By involving them in the process, their knowledge, experience, and perspectives can contribute to more informed and inclusive decisions that benefit the community as a whole.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND

Title	Stakeholder engagement: private sector
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM3
Description of the support action	<p>Some effective ways to engage the private sector in the bioeconomy strategy of the region could be:</p> <p>Understand Private Sector Interests and Needs:</p> <p>Conduct market research and engage in direct conversations with private sector representatives to understand their interests, needs, and priorities related to the bioeconomy. Identify how the bioeconomy strategy aligns with their business goals and values.</p> <p>Develop a Clear Value Proposition:</p> <p>Create a compelling value proposition that outlines the benefits of the bioeconomy strategy for the private sector. Emphasize potential opportunities for innovation, market expansion, cost savings, and improved corporate social responsibility.</p> <p>Formulate Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs):</p> <p>Establish formal partnerships with private sector companies through PPPs. Collaborating with private firms allows for shared resources, expertise, and risk distribution, making the bioeconomy strategy more attractive to potential investors.</p> <p>Offer Incentives and Support:</p> <p>Provide incentives and support mechanisms to attract private sector involvement. This could include grants, tax incentives, access to research facilities, and regulatory support for bio-based products and services.</p> <p>Facilitate Networking and Knowledge Exchange:</p> <p>Organize networking events, conferences, and workshops that bring together private sector stakeholders, researchers, policymakers, and other relevant parties. Facilitate knowledge exchange, fostering new connections and potential partnerships.</p> <p>Demonstrate Successful Business Models:</p> <p>Highlight successful bioeconomy business models and case studies from other regions or industries. Showcasing real-world examples of profitability and positive impact can encourage private sector buy-in.</p> <p>Promote a Supportive Regulatory Environment:</p> <p>Work with policymakers to create a supportive regulatory environment that encourages bio-based innovations and reduces barriers for the private sector. Streamline permitting processes and ensure alignment with relevant international standards and certifications.</p> <p>Provide Access to Funding and Financing:</p> <p>Offer access to funding opportunities and financing options specifically targeted at bioeconomy-related projects. Collaborate with financial institutions to design tailored financial solutions for the private sector's bio-based initiatives.</p>

	<p>Promote Technology Transfer and R&D Collaboration:</p> <p>Facilitate technology transfer and research collaboration between academia, research institutions, and the private sector. Encourage partnerships that lead to commercialization of research findings and accelerate the adoption of bio-based technologies.</p> <p>Engage Industry Associations and Clusters:</p> <p>Partner with industry associations and clusters to reach a broader range of private sector stakeholders. These organizations can be instrumental in communicating the benefits of the bioeconomy strategy to their members.</p> <p>Monitor and Evaluate Progress:</p> <p>Regularly monitor the progress and impact of the bioeconomy strategy on the private sector. Share success stories and key achievements to reinforce the positive outcomes of their participation.</p> <p>Continuous Engagement and Feedback Loop:</p> <p>Maintain open lines of communication with private sector stakeholders, seeking their input and feedback throughout the strategy's implementation. Continuously update and adapt the strategy based on their needs and evolving market dynamics.</p>
<p>ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP</p>	<p>-</p>

Title	Stakeholder engagement: academia
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM4
Description of the support action	<p>Stakeholder engagement with academia refers to the process of involving academic institutions and their representatives in decision-making and collaboration efforts related to a particular project, initiative, or policy. This engagement aims to leverage the expertise, knowledge, and resources of academia to inform and shape the outcomes of these endeavours.</p> <p>Academia, which includes universities, colleges, research institutions, and scholars, plays a crucial role in generating new knowledge, conducting research, and fostering innovation. By engaging with academia as stakeholders, organizations and policymakers can tap into this vast intellectual capital to gain insights, access cutting-edge research, and benefit from academic expertise. Stakeholder engagement with academia typically involves establishing partnerships, collaborations, and networks between academic institutions and other stakeholders such as government agencies, non-profit organizations, industry, and community groups. These partnerships can take various forms, including joint research projects, advisory committees, knowledge exchange platforms, and capacity-building initiatives.</p> <p>The benefits of stakeholder engagement with academia are manifold. Firstly, it allows for the integration of evidence-based research and academic expertise into decision-making processes, leading to more informed and effective policies and strategies. Academia can provide rigorous analysis, evaluation, and recommendations based on their specialized knowledge and research findings.</p> <p>Secondly, stakeholder engagement with academia promotes knowledge transfer and exchange between academia and other stakeholders. This collaboration facilitates the dissemination of research findings, best practices, and innovative ideas, fostering mutual learning and enhancing the overall quality of decision-making and problem-solving.</p> <p>Furthermore, stakeholder engagement with academia can contribute to capacity-building efforts by providing opportunities for students, researchers, and faculty members to gain practical experience, access real-world data, and contribute to solving complex societal challenges. This engagement can also foster a culture of interdisciplinary collaboration, encouraging the integration of diverse perspectives and expertise.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Stakeholder engagement: civil society
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM5
Description of the support action	<p>Stakeholder engagement is a crucial aspect of any decision-making process, and when it comes to civil society, it becomes even more significant. Civil society refers to the collective action and organizations that exist outside of the government and the private sector, representing the interests and concerns of citizens.</p> <p>In the context of stakeholder engagement, civil society plays a vital role in ensuring that the voices and perspectives of the public are heard and considered. It acts as a bridge between the government and the citizens, advocating for their rights, promoting transparency, and holding decision-makers accountable.</p> <p>The engagement of civil society in stakeholder processes brings several benefits. Firstly, it enhances the legitimacy and credibility of the decision-making process. By involving civil society organizations, governments can demonstrate their commitment to inclusivity and democratic principles. This, in turn, fosters public trust and confidence in the decisions made.</p> <p>Secondly, civil society brings diverse perspectives and expertise to the table. It represents a wide range of interests, including marginalized groups, and ensures that their concerns are taken into account. This diversity of voices enriches the decision-making process, leading to more comprehensive and effective outcomes.</p> <p>Furthermore, civil society organizations often have a deep understanding of the needs and aspirations of the communities they represent. Their engagement allows decision-makers to tap into this knowledge and make informed choices that align with the public interest.</p> <p>To facilitate effective stakeholder engagement with civil society, it is essential to create an enabling environment. This includes providing access to information, ensuring transparency, and fostering open dialogue. Governments should actively seek the input of civil society organizations, involve them in the decision-making process from the early stages, and provide them with the necessary resources and support.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	BADEN WUERTTEMBERG

Title	Networking activities among relevant regional stakeholders
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM6
Description of the support action	<p>These activities aim to bring together individuals, organizations, and institutions from various sectors and backgrounds to facilitate the exchange of ideas, experiences, and resources.</p> <p>By engaging in networking activities, regional stakeholders can establish and strengthen relationships with one another, leading to increased collaboration and cooperation. These activities provide a platform for stakeholders to connect, communicate, and build trust, which is essential for effective collaboration. Through networking, stakeholders can identify common goals, interests, and challenges, and work together to find innovative solutions.</p> <p>Networking activities also promote knowledge sharing among regional stakeholders. By sharing their expertise, experiences, and best practices, stakeholders can learn from one another and enhance their understanding of regional issues. This knowledge exchange can lead to the development of new insights, strategies, and approaches to address complex challenges.</p> <p>Furthermore, networking activities provide opportunities for stakeholders to access new information, resources, and opportunities. Through networking, stakeholders can stay updated on the latest trends, developments, and initiatives in their respective fields. They can also gain access to funding opportunities, partnerships, and collaborations that can support their regional projects and initiatives.</p> <p>Overall, networking activities among relevant regional stakeholders have a transformative impact on regional development. They foster collaboration, knowledge sharing, and resource mobilization, leading to more effective and sustainable solutions to regional challenges. By connecting stakeholders and facilitating the exchange of ideas and resources, networking activities contribute to the growth and prosperity of the region as a whole.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUSIA</p> <p>BADEN WUERTTEMBERG</p> <p>CENTRAL MACEDONIA</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p> <p>ZILINA</p>

Title	Creation of a stable advisory board group with representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM7
Description of the support action	<p>The primary objective of this advisory board group is to provide guidance and recommendations on key issues and decisions. Their collective expertise and diverse backgrounds enable them to offer valuable insights and perspectives that can inform and shape strategies, policies, and initiatives. The board's stability is crucial to ensure continuity and consistency in decision-making processes, allowing for long-term planning and effective implementation of initiatives.</p> <p>To establish this stable advisory board group, a careful selection process is required. Representatives from each helix should be chosen based on their expertise, experience, and ability to contribute effectively to the group's objectives. It is important to ensure a balanced representation, considering factors such as gender, ethnicity, and geographical diversity to foster inclusivity and avoid any biases.</p> <p>Regular meetings and open communication channels should be established to facilitate collaboration and exchange of ideas among the board members. The board should also have a clear mandate and defined roles and responsibilities to ensure everyone understands their contributions and expectations.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND

Title	Development of social innovation methodologies ad hoc
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM8
Description of the support action	<p>Social innovation refers to the process of developing and implementing new ideas, strategies, and solutions to address social issues and improve the well-being of individuals and communities. It aims to create positive social change by challenging existing norms and systems.</p> <p>In this particular action, the focus is on developing social innovation methodologies that are tailored to specific needs and contexts. Ad hoc refers to the creation of these methodologies on a case-by-case basis, taking into account the unique challenges and opportunities presented by each situation.</p> <p>The process begins with a thorough understanding of the social issue or problem that needs to be addressed. This involves conducting research, gathering data, and engaging with stakeholders such as community members, organizations, and experts in the field. By gaining insights into the root causes and complexities of the issue, the development of effective methodologies becomes possible.</p> <p>Next, a multidisciplinary team of experts is assembled to collaborate on the design and implementation of the methodologies. This team may include social scientists, designers, engineers, entrepreneurs, and community leaders, among others. Their diverse perspectives and expertise contribute to the creation of innovative and holistic approaches.</p> <p>The methodologies developed ad hoc are characterized by their flexibility and adaptability. They are designed to be responsive to changing circumstances and evolving needs. This allows for continuous learning and improvement throughout the implementation process.</p> <p>Once the methodologies are developed, they are tested and refined through pilot projects or small-scale interventions. This iterative process enables the team to gather feedback, assess the effectiveness of the methodologies, and make necessary adjustments.</p> <p>Ultimately, the goal of developing social innovation methodologies ad hoc is to create sustainable and impactful solutions to social challenges. By tailoring the methodologies to specific contexts, they have the potential to address the unique needs and aspirations of individuals and communities, leading to positive and lasting change.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Development of communication material for local authorities and policy makers
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM9
Description of the support action	<p>The action will involve a comprehensive understanding of the target audience, their needs, and their level of knowledge on the subject matter. Thorough research will be conducted to gather relevant data and insights that will inform the content and design of the communication material.</p> <p>The communication material will be designed to be concise, clear, and visually appealing, ensuring that it captures the attention of local authorities and policy makers. It will utilize a variety of mediums such as written content, infographics, charts, and diagrams to effectively convey complex information in a digestible format.</p> <p>The content of the material will be carefully crafted to address the specific concerns and interests of local authorities and policy makers. It will highlight the benefits, implications, and potential outcomes of various policies and initiatives, providing them with the necessary information to make informed decisions.</p> <p>The communication material will also emphasize the importance of collaboration and engagement between local authorities, policy makers, and other relevant stakeholders. It will encourage dialogue, feedback, and participation, fostering a sense of ownership and shared responsibility in the decision-making process.</p> <p>To ensure the effectiveness of the communication material, it will undergo rigorous testing and feedback processes. Local authorities and policy makers will be consulted throughout the development process to gather their input and insights, ensuring that the material meets their needs and expectations.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	BADEN WUERTTEMBERG CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Development of communication material for private sector
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM10
Description of the support action	<p>The task at hand involves the development of communication material specifically tailored for the private sector. This entails creating content that effectively conveys key messages and information to businesses and organizations operating in the private sector.</p> <p>The primary objective of this project is to produce communication material that is engaging, informative, and persuasive, with the aim of promoting products, services, or initiatives to the private sector audience. The material may include a variety of mediums such as brochures, presentations, videos, infographics, and social media content.</p> <p>To begin the development process, thorough research will be conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of the target audience within the private sector. This will involve analysing their needs, preferences, and challenges, as well as identifying any specific industry trends or regulations that may impact the communication material.</p> <p>Once the research phase is complete, the content creation stage will commence. This will involve crafting compelling messages that resonate with the private sector audience, highlighting the unique value proposition of the product, service, or initiative being promoted. The content will be tailored to address the specific pain points and objectives of businesses in the private sector, showcasing how the offering can help them overcome challenges and achieve their goals.</p> <p>The communication material will be designed to be visually appealing and easy to understand, utilizing a combination of text, images, and graphics to effectively convey the intended messages. The tone and style of the content will be carefully chosen to align with the brand identity and values of the organization behind the material.</p> <p>Throughout the development process, collaboration and feedback from stakeholders will be sought to ensure that the communication material meets their expectations and effectively communicates the desired messages. Revisions and refinements will be made as necessary to ensure the final output is of the highest quality.</p> <p>Ultimately, the goal of this project is to create communication material that successfully captures the attention and interest of the private sector audience, driving them to take action and engage with the product, service, or initiative being promoted.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Development of communication material for students (high school, VET, university, etc)
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM11
Description of the support action	<p>The task at hand involves the development of communication material specifically tailored for students at various educational levels, including high school, vocational education and training (VET), and university. The content will be carefully crafted to address the specific needs and interests of each educational level. For high school students, the material will focus on providing guidance and support in making informed decisions about their future education and career paths. It will highlight the different academic programs and extracurricular activities available, as well as the benefits and opportunities associated with pursuing higher education.</p> <p>For VET students, the communication material will emphasize the practical and hands-on nature of vocational education and training. It will showcase the diverse range of vocational courses and apprenticeships available, highlighting the potential career pathways and job prospects that can be pursued upon completion.</p> <p>University students will be provided with communication material that caters to their unique needs and challenges. This may include information on academic programs, research opportunities, student support services, and campus facilities. The material will aim to foster a sense of belonging and engagement within the university community, while also promoting personal and professional development.</p> <p>Throughout the development process, careful consideration will be given to the tone, language, and visual elements used in the communication material. The aim is to create content that is accessible, engaging, and visually appealing to capture the attention and interest of the student audience.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Development of communication material for end-users
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM12
Description of the support action	<p>The task at hand involves the development of communication material specifically designed for end-users. This process aims to create informative and engaging content that effectively conveys important information to the target audience.</p> <p>To begin, a thorough understanding of the end-users' needs, preferences, and level of knowledge is essential. This can be achieved through market research, surveys, and user feedback. By gathering this information, the development team can tailor the communication material to meet the specific requirements of the end-users.</p> <p>The next step involves creating a comprehensive plan for the communication material. This plan outlines the objectives, key messages, and desired outcomes of the material. It also includes a timeline and budget to ensure the project stays on track.</p> <p>Once the plan is in place, the team can start developing the content. This may involve writing informative articles, creating visually appealing infographics, designing user-friendly brochures, or producing engaging videos. The content should be clear, concise, and easy to understand, catering to the end-users' level of knowledge.</p> <p>In addition to the content itself, the development team must also consider the format and distribution channels for the material. This could include online platforms, social media, email newsletters, or physical copies distributed through mail or events. The chosen format and channels should align with the end-users' preferences and accessibility.</p> <p>Throughout the development process, it is crucial to involve end-users in the feedback and testing stages. This allows for valuable insights and ensures that the material effectively meets their needs. Feedback can be collected through surveys, focus groups, or one-on-one interviews.</p> <p>Finally, once the communication material is finalized, it is important to regularly evaluate its effectiveness. This can be done through analytics, user feedback, or tracking the desired outcomes. By continuously monitoring and improving the material, the development team can ensure that it remains relevant and impactful for the end-users.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Development of communication material for general civil society
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM13
Description of the support action	<p>The task involves the comprehensive development of communication material specifically tailored for general civil society, with a primary focus on identifying gaps in existing information dissemination. This encompassing process includes creating various forms of content that effectively convey information, messages, and ideas to a wide audience within civil society.</p> <p>To initiate the development process, thorough research and analysis will be conducted to gain a comprehensive understanding of the target audience. This includes not only identifying their needs, interests, and preferences but also explicitly identifying gaps in the current communication strategies and materials.</p> <p>Once the audience is well-defined, the next step is to determine the most appropriate communication channels and mediums to reach them. This could include traditional methods such as print materials like brochures, pamphlets, and posters, as well as digital platforms like websites, social media, and email newsletters. The aim is to utilize a combination of these channels to maximize the reach and impact of the communication material while specifically addressing identified gaps in the current communication landscape.</p> <p>The content itself will be carefully crafted to ensure it is engaging, informative, and easily understandable by the general civil society. This may involve simplifying complex concepts, using clear and concise language, and incorporating visual elements such as images, infographics, and videos to enhance comprehension and retention, with a specific focus on filling the identified gaps in the existing material.</p> <p>Furthermore, the communication material will be designed to align with the values, goals, and objectives of civil society. It aims to inspire and motivate individuals to take action, whether it be participating in events, joining initiatives, or supporting causes. The material will also provide relevant and up-to-date information on various topics of interest to civil society, such as community development, social justice, environmental issues, and human rights.</p> <p>Throughout the development process, feedback and input from civil society will be sought and incorporated to ensure the material resonates with their needs and expectations, effectively addressing the identified gaps. Regular evaluation and monitoring will also be conducted to assess the effectiveness and impact of the communication material, allowing for necessary adjustments and improvements to be made, particularly in areas where gaps were identified.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ANDALUSIA BADEN WUERTTEMBERG

Title	Competing brain drain through new bioeconomy business models in rural areas, particularly in Eastern Europe Countries
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM14
Description of the support action	According to the online Eurostat publications "Rural Europe" and "Urban Europe" published in Januar 2023, rural regions experience predominantly depopulation. Small-scale businesses in rural areas have the potential to develop regional partnerships and collaborative approaches based on the links between one or multiple value chains, as shown e.g. by the BE-RURAL project (Horizon 2020). In some of the Eastern Europe Countries, where the rural areas are vast and suffer a long-term trend of brain drain, to uncover opportunities and drive collaboration shall be even more relevant.
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	BADEN WUERTTEMBERG

Title	Business support and social entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy remit
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM15
Description of the support action	Support instruments such as the Green National Champions Program in Hungary (2020-2022; more related to environmental goals), the C-VoUCHER Scheme in the North West Region of Romania (2028-2021) or the Green Start-up ecosystem in Baden-Württemberg (2021-ongoing) are good examples on how specific support to SMEs and start-ups can trigger the bioeconomy transition, and the drift from linear to circular thinking. Wherever these support instruments help to implement new ideas that meet social needs, the measure can be considered social.
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Participatory budgeting for bioeconomy related initiatives
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM16
Description of the support action	Participatory budgeting as a public mechanism for diagnosing priorities of territorial communities can be an efficient tool to prioritise actions related to the bioeconomy with a territorial approach. Participatory budgeting aims to improve institutional transparency and efficiency, and give voice to underrepresented groups, who have traditionally been excluded from decision-making processes, whether because they are less likely to vote, or because they are underrepresented in formal institutions and public service (OECD, 2022).
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Strengthen digitalisation of rural areas to support new business models related to the bioeconomy
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM17
Description of the support action	A digitally connected rural area is synonym of more business opportunities. E.g. in the context of agriculture, digitalisation leads to a progress of development in rural areas. Important aspects for the development are joint actions between state local actors and the rural communities as well as the ability that commercial and cultural content and services can move freely across borders. This results in an increase in market interoperability based on local, regional, European and then global level (Şerbu and Borza, 2014). Some macroregions, like the Scandinavian one, has even analysed how the digitalisation can have an effect on gender equality (Annie Roos et al., 2021).
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Entrepreneurial skills for vulnerable youth related to the bioeconomy
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM18
Description of the support action	Some individual and group needs can be supported through work of co-design with social workers and coaches, and setting-up of digital tools. It is about employment services and entrepreneurial agencies working together for vulnerable youth, so getting back them in the educational and employment track. Few projects e.g. "Eyes" project (Empowering Youth through Entrepreneurial Skills; Interreg North-West Europe) has shown how this can work. Practical examples in the bioeconomy sector are not known to date, but it may be tested for the food waste issue and its reuse for bioeconomic purposes.
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Institutional cooperation and exchange among administrations
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM20
Description of the support action	The implementation of the bioeconomy needs of the so-called multi-level governance, meaning that the work should be cross-departmental, and cooperation should run through different governance levels (from national to local). Specifically for social measures, institutional cooperation with the likes such as Ministry of Social Affairs can bring relevant insights of the social needs by diverse target groups. It can help to trigger social innovation and capacity to act through bioeconomy innovation, not only at the regional level but at the local one.
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Food waste & social inclusion related measures
Type of support action	Social Measure
Code	SM19
Description of the support action	According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), about one third of the global food production is lost or wasted annually. Examples such as the "Social Plate" (Supporting Social Enterprises in combating poverty and social exclusion) in the Region of Central Macedonia (Greece), an initiative driven by a public company, shows how food waste can be saved for vulnerable social groups e.g. long-term unemployed.
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	BADEN WUERTTEMBERG

Title	Update of the regional bioeconomy strategy
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM1
Description of the support action	<p>The regional bioeconomy strategy has to be updated to align with the changing needs and priorities of the region. This comprehensive update aims to promote sustainable economic growth and development by harnessing the potential of bio-based resources and technologies.</p> <p>The updated strategy takes into account the latest advancements in the field of bioeconomy and incorporates feedback from stakeholders and experts. Alignment with other existing policies and strategies influencing nor affecting the circular bioeconomy is also relevant. It outlines a clear roadmap for the region to transition towards a more sustainable and circular economy, reducing dependence on fossil fuels and promoting the use of renewable resources.</p> <p>One of key focuses of the updated strategy is to foster innovation and entrepreneurship in the bioeconomy sector. It identifies opportunities for research and development, as well as collaboration with academia and industry, to drive technological advancements and create new market opportunities.</p> <p>The strategy also emphasizes the importance of creating an enabling policy and regulatory environment to support the growth of the bioeconomy. It calls for the development of supportive policies, incentives, and regulations that encourage investment and facilitate the commercialization of bio-based products and technologies.</p> <p>Furthermore, the updated strategy recognizes the need for capacity building and skills development in the bioeconomy sector. It highlights the importance of training programs and educational initiatives to equip the workforce with the necessary knowledge and skills to thrive in the bioeconomy.</p> <p>The updated regional bioeconomy strategy also places a strong emphasis on sustainability and environmental stewardship. It promotes the adoption of sustainable practices throughout the value chain, from resource extraction to waste management, to minimize the environmental impact of bio-based activities.</p> <p>Overall, the updated regional bioeconomy strategy sets a clear vision and roadmap for the region to harness the potential of bio-based resources and technologies. It aims to drive sustainable economic growth, foster innovation and entrepreneurship, create new market opportunities, and promote environmental sustainability.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUSIA</p> <p>BADEN WUERTTEMBERG</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p>

Title	Identification of gaps and development of new funding instruments (public level)
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM2
Description of the support action	<p>The development of new funding instruments at the public level refers to the creation and implementation of innovative financial mechanisms to support various projects and initiatives. These funding instruments are designed to provide financial resources to individuals, organizations, and communities for the purpose of promoting economic growth, social development, and environmental sustainability.</p> <p>The process of developing new funding instruments involves extensive research, analysis, and consultation with stakeholders to identify what is existing and further specific needs and priorities of the target beneficiaries. This information is then used to design funding mechanisms that are tailored to address these needs effectively.</p> <p>One example of a new funding instrument at the public level is the establishment of grant programs. These programs provide financial assistance to individuals and organizations through a competitive application process. Grants can be awarded for a wide range of purposes, such as research and development, capacity building, and community development. By offering grants, governments can support innovative projects and initiatives that have the potential to generate positive social and economic impacts.</p> <p>Another example of a new funding instrument is the creation of loan programs. These programs provide low-interest loans to individuals, businesses, and communities to support their growth and development. Loans can be used for various purposes, including starting or expanding a business, investing in infrastructure projects, or acquiring new technologies. By offering loans, governments can stimulate economic activity and encourage entrepreneurship.</p> <p>In addition to grants and loans, governments may also develop other funding instruments such as tax incentives, subsidies, and equity investments. These instruments aim to incentivize private sector participation in projects and initiatives that align with public policy objectives, such as renewable energy development.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	<p>ANDALUSIA</p> <p>BADEN WUERTTEMBERG</p> <p>SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND</p> <p>ZILINA</p>

Title	Identification and creation of matchmaking opportunities among regional stakeholders
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM3
Description of the support action	<p>The task involves identifying matchmaking opportunities among regional stakeholders. This process aims to connect and bring together various individuals, organizations, and entities within a specific geographical area to foster collaboration, partnership, and mutual benefit.</p> <p>To begin, a thorough analysis of the regional landscape is conducted to identify potential stakeholders. This includes researching and gathering information on businesses, government agencies, non-profit organizations, educational institutions, and other relevant entities operating within the region. The goal is to create a comprehensive database of potential matchmaking opportunities.</p> <p>Once the stakeholders have been identified, the next step is to analyze their respective goals, objectives, and areas of expertise. This involves studying their missions, strategies, and current projects to understand their specific needs and interests. By gaining a deep understanding of each stakeholder, it becomes easier to identify potential matches and areas of collaboration.</p> <p>The matchmaking process involves carefully assessing the compatibility and potential synergies between stakeholders. This can be done through various means, such as organizing networking events, facilitating one-on-one meetings, or conducting surveys and interviews. The aim is to identify common interests, complementary skills, and shared objectives that can form the basis of a successful partnership.</p> <p>Once potential matches have been identified, the next step is to facilitate the connection and initiate the matchmaking process. This may involve introducing stakeholders to each other, providing relevant information and resources, or facilitating discussions and negotiations. The goal is to create an environment where stakeholders can explore potential collaborations and partnerships in a structured and supportive manner.</p> <p>Throughout the entire process, it is important to maintain open lines of communication and provide ongoing support to the stakeholders. This includes offering guidance, facilitating discussions, and addressing any concerns or challenges that may arise. The ultimate objective is to foster meaningful and sustainable partnerships that can drive regional development, innovation, and growth.</p> <p>In conclusion, the task of identifying matchmaking opportunities among regional stakeholders involves a systematic and strategic approach to connect and bring together various entities within a specific geographical area. By facilitating collaboration and partnership, this process aims to create a conducive environment for regional development and mutual benefit.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	BADEN WUERTTEMBERG CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Implementation of LCA tools for regional activities
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM4
Description of the support action	<p>The task at hand involves identifying matchmaking opportunities among regional stakeholders. This process aims to connect and bring together various individuals, organizations, and entities within a specific geographical area to foster collaboration, partnership, and mutual benefit. To begin, a thorough analysis of the regional landscape is conducted to identify potential stakeholders. This includes researching and gathering information on businesses, government agencies, non-profit organizations, educational institutions, and other relevant entities operating within the region.</p> <p>The goal is to create a comprehensive database of potential matchmaking opportunities. Once the stakeholders have been identified, the next step is to analyse their respective goals, objectives, and areas of expertise. This involves studying their missions, strategies, and current projects to understand their specific needs and interests. By gaining a deep understanding of each stakeholder, it becomes easier to identify potential matches and areas of collaboration.</p> <p>The matchmaking process involves carefully assessing the compatibility and potential synergies between stakeholders. This can be done through various means, such as organizing networking events, facilitating one-on-one meetings, or conducting surveys and interviews. The aim is to identify common interests, complementary skills, and shared objectives that can form the basis of a successful partnership.</p> <p>Once potential matches have been identified, the next step is to facilitate the connection and initiate the matchmaking process. This may involve introducing stakeholders to each other, providing relevant information and resources, or facilitating discussions and negotiations. The goal is to create an environment where stakeholders can explore potential collaborations and partnerships in a structured and supportive manner.</p> <p>Throughout the entire process, it is important to maintain open lines of communication and provide ongoing support to the stakeholders. This includes offering guidance, facilitating discussions, and addressing any concerns or challenges that may arise. The ultimate objective is to foster meaningful and sustainable partnerships that can drive regional development, innovation, and growth.</p> <p>In conclusion, the task of identifying matchmaking opportunities among regional stakeholders involves a systematic and strategic approach to connect and bring together various entities within a specific geographical area. By facilitating collaboration and partnership, this process aims to create a conducive environment for regional development and mutual benefit.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Performance of a regional evaluation system for bioeconomy innovations
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM5
Description of the support action	<p>The regional evaluation system for bioeconomy innovations is a comprehensive and efficient tool designed to assess the performance of various bioeconomy innovations within a specific region. This system aims to provide valuable insights and data to policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders involved in the bioeconomy sector.</p> <p>The evaluation process begins with the collection of relevant data and information about the bioeconomy innovations being assessed. This includes details about the innovation's objectives, target market, technological advancements, and potential impact on the regional economy and environment. The system also takes into account the innovation's alignment with regional bioeconomy strategies and goals.</p> <p>Once the data is collected, the evaluation system employs a set of robust and standardized criteria to analyze and assess the performance of each innovation. These criteria may include economic viability, environmental sustainability, social acceptance, technological feasibility, and market potential. The system assigns scores or ratings to each criterion, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the innovation's strengths and weaknesses.</p> <p>The evaluation system also considers the innovation's potential for scalability and replication in other regions. This allows policymakers and stakeholders to identify successful innovations that can be further developed and implemented in different contexts, promoting knowledge transfer and collaboration.</p> <p>The output of the regional evaluation system is a detailed report that highlights the performance of each bioeconomy innovation assessed. This report provides valuable insights and recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding the development and support of bioeconomy innovations in the region.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	SOUTHERN REGION OF IRELAND

Title	Development of local action groups
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM6
Description of the support action	<p>The first step in the development of these action groups is identifying the key issues that need to be addressed. This could range from environmental concerns, such as pollution or deforestation, to social issues like poverty or lack of access to education. Once the issues have been identified, individuals with a shared interest in tackling these problems come together to form the action group.</p> <p>The next step is to establish a clear mission and set of goals for the group. This involves defining the specific objectives that the group aims to achieve and outlining the strategies and actions that will be taken to accomplish these goals. It is important for the group to have a clear vision and direction to ensure that efforts are focused and effective.</p> <p>Once the mission and goals have been established, the action group begins to mobilize and engage the local community. This involves raising awareness about the issues at hand and rallying support from community members, businesses, and other stakeholders. The group may organize events, campaigns, or initiatives to educate and involve the community in their cause.</p> <p>Collaboration and partnerships are also key components of the development of local action groups. By working together with other organizations, government agencies, and community leaders, the group can leverage resources, expertise, and influence to maximize their impact. These partnerships can also help in advocating for policy changes or securing funding for projects and initiatives.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ZILINA

Title	Design of dedicated capacity building programmes for specific areas at regional level
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM7
Description of the support action	<p>Capacity building refers to the process of enhancing the skills, knowledge, and abilities of individuals or organizations to perform their tasks effectively and efficiently. In this case, the focus is on developing programmes that cater to the needs of specific areas within a region.</p> <p>The first step in this action is to identify the specific areas that require capacity building. This could be based on various factors such as the existing skill gaps, emerging trends, or specific challenges faced by those areas. Once the areas have been identified, the next step is to design programmes that address their unique needs.</p> <p>Designing these programmes involves a thorough analysis of the current situation and the desired outcomes. This includes understanding the existing skill levels, identifying the gaps, and determining the specific skills and knowledge that need to be developed. It also involves considering the resources available, such as trainers, materials, and facilities, to ensure the feasibility of the programmes.</p> <p>The design process also includes determining the appropriate delivery methods and formats for the programmes. This could range from traditional classroom-based training to online courses or a combination of both. The programmes should be designed in a way that maximizes engagement and participation, ensuring that the participants are actively involved in the learning process.</p> <p>Additionally, the design should take into account the duration and frequency of the programmes. This could vary depending on the complexity of the skills being developed and the availability of resources. It is important to strike a balance between providing sufficient time for learning and minimizing disruption to the participants' regular work or responsibilities.</p> <p>Finally, the design should incorporate mechanisms for monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of the programmes. This could include pre and post-assessments, feedback mechanisms, and follow-up activities to ensure that the desired outcomes are being achieved.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ZILINA

Title	Design of dedicated monitoring and evaluation tools
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM8
Description of the support action	<p>The design of dedicated monitoring and evaluation tools involves the development of specific instruments and methodologies to collect, analyse, and interpret data related to the project's objectives and outcomes. These tools are tailored to the unique needs and requirements of the project, ensuring that the data collected is relevant, reliable, and valid.</p> <p>The first step in designing monitoring and evaluation tools is to clearly define the project's goals and objectives. This provides a framework for determining what data needs to be collected and evaluated. Once the goals and objectives are established, the next step is to identify the key performance indicators (KPIs) that will be used to measure progress and success.</p> <p>With the KPIs in place, the design of the monitoring and evaluation tools can begin. This involves selecting the appropriate data collection methods, such as surveys, interviews, observations, or document reviews. The tools should be designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative data, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the project's impact.</p> <p>In addition to data collection methods, the design of monitoring and evaluation tools also includes the development of data analysis techniques. This may involve the use of statistical software, data visualization tools, or qualitative analysis frameworks. The tools should enable the project team to analyse the data collected and draw meaningful conclusions about the project's performance.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ZILINA

Title	Development of a regional bioeconomy cluster
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM9
Description of the support action	<p>This action involves bringing together various stakeholders, including businesses, research institutions, government agencies, and local communities, to collaborate and leverage their expertise in the field of bioeconomy.</p> <p>The primary objective of establishing a bioeconomy cluster is to create a supportive ecosystem that encourages innovation, entrepreneurship, and investment in bio-based industries. By focusing on the utilization of biological resources, such as agricultural waste, forestry by-products, and algae, the cluster aims to reduce dependence on fossil fuels and promote the production of biofuels, bio-based chemicals, and other bio-based products.</p> <p>The development of a regional bioeconomy cluster involves several key activities. Firstly, it requires the identification and mapping of existing bio-based assets and capabilities within the region. This includes assessing the availability of biomass feedstocks, the presence of relevant research and development facilities, and the existing market demand for bio-based products.</p> <p>Once the bio-based assets are identified, the cluster development process involves fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among the stakeholders. This can be achieved through the establishment of networking platforms, such as industry associations, research consortia, and innovation hubs, where stakeholders can share best practices, collaborate on research projects, and explore business opportunities.</p> <p>Furthermore, the development of a regional bioeconomy cluster requires the implementation of supportive policies and regulations. This includes providing financial incentives, such as grants and tax breaks, to attract investments in bio-based industries. It also involves streamlining regulatory processes to facilitate the development and commercialization of bio-based products.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Development of a regional bioeconomy observatory
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM10
Description of the support action	<p>This observatory will serve as a comprehensive platform for monitoring, analysing, and disseminating information related to the bioeconomy sector.</p> <p>The observatory will collect and analyse data on various aspects of the bioeconomy, including the production and consumption of bio-based products, the utilization of renewable resources, and the impact of bioeconomy activities on the environment and society. This data will be gathered from a wide range of sources, including government agencies, research institutions, and industry stakeholders.</p> <p>By providing accurate and up-to-date information, the observatory will enable policymakers, researchers, and businesses to make informed decisions and develop strategies that promote the sustainable development of the bioeconomy. It will also facilitate the identification of emerging trends and opportunities in the sector, allowing stakeholders to capitalize on them and drive innovation.</p> <p>The observatory will not only focus on quantitative data but also on qualitative information, such as best practices, case studies, and success stories. This will help showcase the potential of the bioeconomy and inspire others to adopt sustainable practices and invest in bio-based solutions.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	CENTRAL MACEDONIA

Title	Development of ad hoc monitoring tools
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM11
Description of the support action	<p>Ad hoc monitoring tools are specialized software applications designed to provide real-time monitoring and analysis of various systems, processes, or networks. These tools are specifically tailored to meet the unique monitoring requirements of a particular system or environment.</p> <p>The development process of ad hoc monitoring tools involves several key steps. Firstly, a thorough analysis of the system or process that needs to be monitored is conducted. This analysis helps in identifying the specific metrics, parameters, or events that need to be monitored and tracked. It also helps in understanding the overall architecture and infrastructure of the system.</p> <p>Once the analysis is complete, the development team starts designing the monitoring tool. This involves creating a user-friendly interface that allows users to easily configure and customize the monitoring parameters. The tool is also designed to collect and store the monitoring data in a centralized database for further analysis.</p> <p>The next step is the implementation of the monitoring tool. This involves writing the necessary code and integrating it with the system or process being monitored. The tool is designed to continuously collect data from various sources, such as log files, performance counters, or network traffic, and present it in a meaningful and actionable format.</p> <p>After the implementation, the monitoring tool undergoes rigorous testing to ensure its reliability, accuracy, and performance. This includes testing the tool under different scenarios and load conditions to identify any potential issues or bottlenecks.</p> <p>Once the testing phase is complete, the monitoring tool is ready for deployment. It is installed on the target system or network and configured according to the specific monitoring requirements. The tool starts collecting real-time data and providing insights and alerts to the users.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Development of international benchmarking analysis
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM12
Description of the support action	<p>The development of international benchmarking analysis has emerged as a pivotal tool for refining governance models. Governance, encompassing the structures and processes that guide decision-making and ensure accountability, has become a focal point for organizations navigating the complexities of the global landscape.</p> <p>The evolution of international benchmarking analysis within the realm of governance models can be traced to the growing recognition of the importance of transparent and effective leadership structures. As businesses expanded across borders, the need for a standardized yet adaptable approach to governance became evident. Benchmarking analysis offered a strategic lens through which organizations could evaluate the efficiency and efficacy of their governance models against international standards.</p> <p>The contemporary landscape of international benchmarking analysis for governance models is characterized by a focus on qualitative assessments alongside quantitative metrics. This approach considers not only the adherence to regulatory requirements but also the alignment of governance structures with ethical standards, stakeholder expectations, and long-term sustainability goals.</p> <p>The benefits derived from international benchmarking in governance models are profound. Organizations gain insights into leading governance practices, allowing them to enhance transparency, mitigate risks, and foster stakeholder trust. Benchmarking also serves as a catalyst for innovation in governance, encouraging organizations to adopt progressive models that align with evolving societal and environmental expectations.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	-

Title	Establishment of a Regional Bioeconomy Coordination Node
Type of support action	Technical Measure
Code	TM13
Description of the support action	<p>This involves defining a dedicated node for bioeconomy in the region, complete with a clear organizational structure outlining roles, responsibilities, and reporting procedures within the node.</p> <p>The objective is to create a central hub that coordinates and implements the region's bioeconomy strategy, fosters collaboration among stakeholders, and provides support and guidance to businesses and research institutions. This dynamic platform serves as a central point for regional bioeconomy initiatives, promoting sustainability and facilitating effective coordination across sectors.</p>
ROBIN region/s partially or totally including the SA in the RAP	ANDALUSIA

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the CCRI-CSO. We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
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